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D8.4 Application-specific gateways, developed in the second release

FINAL REPORT

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2 Status and Change History

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2.13	29/7/2013	All	All	Second round of comments by G. Terstyanszky are incorporated
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3 Glossary

BPMN	Business Process Model and Notation
CO	Confidential
DCI	Distributed Computing Infrastructures
DG	Desktop Grid
DoW	Description of Work
GAM	General Administration Manager
JRA	Joint Research Activity
NA	Networking Activity
TMB	Technical Management Board
PDF	Portable Document Format
PMB	Project Management Board
PU	Public
QR	Quality Reviewer
SA	Service Activity
SG	Service Grid
SVN	Subversion, version control system
WP	Workpackage

4 Introduction

The main objective of WP8 (JRA2) is to develop the application-specific gateways based on the generic gateway technology provided by WP7 (JRA1). The gateways are deployed and operated by WP4 (SA1). This deliverable reports on the development of the **second** release of the application-specific gateways, based on the experience with the first release and on user requests.

Deliverable D8.3 gives a short overview of features, portlets and workflows developed for the second release.

All individual gateways depend on the generic technology provided by JRA1:

- WS-PGRADE
- gUSE
- Liferay

The implementation language is JAVA but the individual portals depend on various other external components and have different dependencies. The overall architecture for JRA2 is shown in Figure 1. Each gateway has specialized on certain components. The architecture did not change from the first release of the gateways, as reported in D8.2:

Figure 1: Overall generic architecture.

5 Gateways

The report has a structure with the following sections for each of the gateway development tasks:

1. User Feedback, Experience
2. Existing Setup and Features in 1st Release
3. Additional Features in 2nd Release
4. Status and Plans for Final Release

5.1 JRA2.1 Statistical Seismology Science Gateway (METU)

The Statistical Seismology Science Gateway (*SSS-Gateway*) aims to provide a comprehensive set of statistical methods for the field of seismology in such a way that skilled users can develop their own seismology models by accessing the gateway services, while novice users can easily use the existing applications. *SSS-Gateway* is developed on top of the generic-purpose gateway services of *WS-PGRADE/gUSE*.

This science gateway aims to implement the following advanced statistical seismology functions (SSFs), reflecting the latest advances in the literature, for the international seismology community:

- SSF1: Integration of multi-source data for increased reliability and quality
- SSF2: Determination of probability distributions and their input parameters
- SSF3: Robust techniques for the parameter estimation in models and relations
- SSF4: Complex predictive modeling of earthquakes in time-space domains
- SSF5: Ground motion prediction equations
- SSF6: Logic-tree and sensitivity analysis in probabilistic seismic hazard assessment
- SSF7: Statistical calculations for seismic risk

The functions listed above are implemented by, called *SSF Workflows*, and the gateway offers a choice of three service levels for its users with different skills to access these *SSF Workflows*:

- *Simple*: A user can run and get the result of any of SSFs for her/his data and parameters easily through the GUI provided by the simple-use portlets, one per SSF. They allow users to easily upload input files and manage parameters of *SSF Workflows* and also give them chance to examine the results directly with or without downloading.
- *Advanced*: A user can code her/his models in a programming language (such as FORTRAN, C/C++) calling any combination of the web services provided to access the *SSF Workflows*. This level of service is provided by the advanced-use portlet.
- *Expert*: A user can design and use her/his own improved workflows by embedding the *SSF Workflows* provided. Expert users can have their own high-level, improved workflows by embedding the *SSF Workflows*. They can also manage their own datasets through these portlets.

While the portlets of simple and advanced service levels are developed within the frame of this customised gateway, the expert-use support is purely provided by the generic *WS-PGRADE* portlets. For executing the *SSF Workflows*, users need to submit a valid certificate to access a European DCI, such as the Turkish Grid. Alternatively, for relatively short runs and trial purposes only, a user can directly run SFFs on the local cluster “Pomegranate” even when the user holds no certificate.

5.1.1 User Feedback, Experience

The first release of SSS-Gateway was deployed in production at the beginning of 2013 and it has been up with the first five SSF Workflows, their simple-use portlets and the advanced-use portlet since then. The services given have been disseminated and announced in many events, in addition to mailing lists and web. Accordingly, many users from the local institutes, European organizations and even editors of seismology journals have been joined.

The application-specific helpdesk functionality is provided via a discussion forum on the gateway as well as a contact e-mail address, the latter of which has been preferred by the users heavily. The comments and feedbacks collected can be summarized as follows:

- The user guide is too much detailed and too long for a new user to start with. It would be better and easier to learn how to use the gateway with help of a simpler document and sample inputs (files and parameters).
- Outputs of many simple-use portlets can be fed into some others as input files. This needs successive download and then upload operations performed by users. Instead, these result files could be copied and used by the portlets themselves in case of user requests.
- Some further statistical methods and models could be added to the existing SSFs, such as:
 - Maximum Curvature and Entire Magnitude Range catalog completeness techniques and also alternative aftershock/foreshock elimination methods to SSF1.
 - Characteristic earthquake magnitude distribution to SSF4.
 - Parameter estimation of magnitude conversion equations used in SSF1.
 - Renewal and Renewal Hybrid models for seismic hazard assessment to SSF4.
 - Parameter estimation of probability density functions of interarrival times to SSF2 and SSF3.
 - A set of new attenuation relations to SSF5.
- The portlets could be improved regarding the following aspects:
 - Better, more explanatory, error reports or messages for both job execution and SSF outputs.
 - Support for other types of seismic sources (such as line and background sources) in addition to area sources.
 - More effective (smarter) job monitoring interface.

5.1.2 Existing Setup and Features in 1st Release

The first release of SSS-Gateway, when deployed, was operational with

- The workflows of the functions SSF1, SSF2, SSF3 and SFF4;
- Four, so called, simple-use portlets for the SSFs listed above, each providing GUI-based access to the associated SSF;
- The advanced-use portlet, providing an environment where users can run their own models written in C, C++ or FORTRAN calling any combination of the implemented SSF Workflows, as if they were functions.

Though it was originally planned to include SSF5 in the first release, its development was delayed mostly due to the complexity of the models included. Hence, the SSF5 Workflow and its simple-use portlet was added to the gateway one month after the first release.

5.1.3 Additional Features in 2nd Release

After deploying the first release, many features have been reviewed and revised, considering the user feedbacks, and developments of the remaining functions have been started:

- As the mechanisms connecting SSF4 and SSF5 seemed inappropriate for some scenarios that users might have, this connection and the SSF5 portlet itself were enhanced (Figure 2).

Figure 2: The SSF5 portlet, enhanced version for the second release.

Figure 3: User is notified that SSF1 can be used to produce the input catalog for SSF2.

- Its URL has been changed from the Turkish Science Grid domain to the METU address as <http://seismo.ceng.metu.edu.tr>. Meanwhile, the underlying WS-PGRADE/gUSE suite was upgraded to 3.5.4.
- The data flow technique was renewed considerably. Now, a user who wants to give the output of an SSF portlet to another one does not need to download and upload it. When there is a chance of using some other SSF portlet to produce an input data file for the current, the user is notified with an option of running that portlet first (**Figure 3**). Similarly, if such an output data file has already been produced by a portlet, then the current SSF portlet will provide a quick button through which the existing data file can be used as input directly (**Figure 4**).
- The Quick Guide was prepared, together with some sample input data files, and published at <http://seismo.ceng.metu.edu.tr/documentation>. With the help of them, an inexperienced user can easily try the gateway.
- Many additional statistical methods/models addressed by the users or selected by the domain experts have been implemented and added to the related SSFs. As an example Renewal and Renewal Hybrid models added to SSF4 can be depicted in **Figure 5**.
- Developments of the SSF6 and SSF7 Workflows together with their simple-use portlets have been started. Though their developments take a bit longer than planned, the second release is expected to include SSF6 and SSF7.

Figure 4: User can directly use the existing output file of SSF1 as an input catalog for SSF2.

Figure 5: The SSF4 simple-use portlet.

5.1.4 SSS-Gateway Status and Plans for the Final Release

The major steps of the SSS-Gateway development, limited to the JRA2 activities, are summarized in the table below:

Task	Month	Status
WS-PGRADE/gUSE Installation	M1	Done M1
Startup and Development Plan	M2	Done M2
Test Plan – Initial	M2	Done M2
Requirements Analysis	M3	Done M3
Architectural Design	M3	Done M4
SSF1 (Workflow + Simple-use Portlet)	M4	Done M6
SSF2 (Workflow + Simple-use Portlet)	M5	Done M7
Advanced-use Portlet	M6	Done M7
SSF3 (Workflow + Simple-use Portlet)	M7	Done M8
Review & Revise – I	M8	Done M9
SA2 Test Integration Started	M9	Done M9
SSF4 (Workflow + Simple-use Portlet)	M10	Done M11
SSF5 (Workflow + Simple-use Portlet)	M11	Done M16
Review & Revise – II	M12-M14	Done M15
First Release	M14	Done M15
Review & Revise – III	M15	Done M16
SSF6 (Workflow + Simple-use Portlet)	M16-M17	In Progress
SSF7 (Workflow + Simple-use Portlet)	M18-M19	In Progress
Review & Revise - IV	M20-M26	In Progress
Second Release	M26	
Review & Revise - V	M27-M34	
Final Release	M34	

Since a kind of incremental model is followed, while new SSFs are being developed, the current features are also improved considering user feedbacks in each release cycle. Accordingly, at the same time as it is operated by SA1, all the comments, suggestions, bug reports, feature requests and feedbacks of the users and domain experts have been collected and input to the revision process.

Together with its second release, the Statistical Seismology Science Gateway is planned to be fully operational providing all the workflows and portlets initially planned. Thus, the final release is expected to reflect the results of the revision process based on the user feedbacks.

5.1.5 Operation and Testing Status

The operational and testing status of SSS-Gateway can be stated briefly as below:

- SA1 currently operates this science gateway with the first five SSFs and advanced-use portlet on which users can code their own models calling the statistical seismology functions provided.
- As a part of the user support facilities, the user manual, quick guide with sample input files, demo videos, discussion forum and contact e-mail address are provided.
- The portal is integrated to the SA2 test system. Each portlet constructed is sent to SA2 for testing. The web-tests defined are run weekly for each portlet.
- The workflows for the functions SSF6 and SSF7, together with their simple-use portlets, are still under construction. Their test inputs are also being prepared for SA2. All of them are expected to be ready in September 2013 together with the second release.
- Considering user feedbacks as well as comments of the domain experts, all the features are reviewed and revised repeatedly. This process will be continued even after the second release.
- Cloud integration is also planned for the next months as a part of this revision process.

5.2 JRA2.2 Swiss Systems Biology Community Science Gateway (ETH Zurich)

The Swiss Proteomics Portal existed as a Gridsphere-based P-GRADE solution at the time when SCI-BUS has started. We have ported the existing portal to the WS-PGRADE Liferay-based technology. The motivation to move to a more scalable and better maintainable system comes from the very large amounts of data produced by the Swiss Systems Biology initiative, SystemsX.ch.

We call the new portal iPortal and it is running at <https://iportal.ethz.ch>.

The already existing workflows have been rewritten in the WS-PGRADE based system. Several new workflows have been implemented, as well as dedicated portlets for better user experience:

- Workflow submission wizard. This is a very proteomics specific set of pages guiding the users through the configuration of existing concrete workflows.
- Data management portlet (openBIS interaction).
- Monitoring portlet for simple job monitoring. This portlet shows the monitoring information in a simplified manner to our users so that they are not overload with too much information as in the generic monitor. It also allows administrative users to see and rescue other user's jobs, which is great for support activities.
- Infrastructure initialization portlet.
- Workflow testing portlet.

5.2.1 User Feedback, Experience

Since we started to operate our service on production level we has been trying for establish close collaboration with the lab members, the users of our service. We regularly present the new features, developments on group seminars and write them in the weekly IT newsletter of the group. We also try to involve group members early in the development phase and ask them to test the latest developments.

In the following list we try to summarize what we learned from these feedbacks:

- There are users who run several analyses on the same datasets to improve their results or try out different parameters. They often use large datasets. Therefore they need a solution for quick dataset selection, reusing earlier selections.
- Our workflows use several different software packages and the update of different components of the system can cause stability problems. It is essential that we provide our service as stable as possible and our workflows should provide consistent results.
- As the number of the users increased we experienced some problems with different tool, parameter and dataset combinations, where the intermediate data files can be invalid or corrupt for certain combinations of input parameters. In such cases more

flexible ways to troubleshoot these problems are needed, so that the user can understand what parameters need to be changed for correct results.

- Some of the workflows require search databases as input for the analysis. For the proper versioned handling of these databases we developed a system called BioDB and integrated it to the portal. We got requests to extend the functionality of this service.
- We also got several requests to introduce new workflows or extend the functionality of the current workflows. For example one of these requests was to provide some way to visualize the results provided by our search workflows.

5.2.2 Existing Setup and Features in 1st Release

The iPortal is an application-oriented portal, which has been customized to meet the needs of the Systems Biology community. We are mostly using the ASM API of gUSE and have written our own portlets in Liferay.

For the first release we have already documented in D8.2 the following portlets:

- **Workflow Wizard portlet.** We have developed a dedicated interface for the users to guide them through the selection of a predefined workflow, a dataset to run on and its parametrization.
- **Monitoring portlet.** We have also developed a separate monitoring portlet that allows for administration views and also easier navigation and log view than the generic built-in monitor from WS-PGRADE.
- **Login and initialization portlet.** At first-time login, we request the user to log in on the local cluster infrastructure with their own account. This portlet creates a new keypair which is then used in future sessions of the user to access the local cluster.

In terms of workflows, we had the following workflows in place:

- Several workflows for protein search in MS/MS data, depending on the dataset and instrument type
- Two experimental workflows for quantification using OpenMS.

5.2.3 Additional Features in 2nd Release

Several extensions and developments have been done since we introduced iPortal. These developments made in the last period were mainly related to the feedback we got from our users and summarized in the previous section.

- **Upgrade of the Workflow Wizard Portlet:** The OpenBIS data-selector was extended with two data pre-selectors which enable users to quickly find and select their datasets for analysis. One of them provides access to the tagging feature of OpenBIS that enables to select arbitrary dataset groups by associated names in one click. The other selector is based on the data hierarchy in OpenBIS (Project/Experiment/Sample) and allows quick selection of datasets by navigating through the data tree.

Step 3: Select the Data Choose

Dataset Tag Selector
 metaprojecttest taggingtest Note: Use Show Dataset to check whether the selected tags reference dataset which are compatible with this workflow.

Biological Sample Based Preselection
 OpenBis Space: CHLUDWIG OpenBis Project: UPS

Biological Experiments:		Biological Samples:				
CODE	COMMENTNAME	CODE	SAMPLE_TYPE	NAME	COMMENT	EXPER
E278534	UPS1	MTB_TOTAL_PROTEOME	BIOLOGICAL_BASIC	Mtb_total_proteome_SWATH		/CHLUDV
E278537	UPS2	S278538	BIOLOGICAL_SAMPLE	UPS1_SWATH_DDA	UPS1 in Mtb background	/CHLUDV
		S278539	BIOLOGICAL_SAMPLE	UPS1_SWATH	UPS1 in Mtb background	/CHLUDV
		S278540	BIOLOGICAL_SAMPLE	UPS2_SWATH	UPS2 in Mtb background	/CHLUDV
		S278541	BIOLOGICAL_SAMPLE	UPS2_SRM	UPS2 in Mtb background	/CHLUDV
		S278615	BIOLOGICAL_SAMPLE	Orbi_DDA		/CHLUDV

OpenBis dataset selection: Settings Refresh Select All Clear Selection 7 files are selected.

BIO_EXPERIMENT	CODE	CENTROIDED	FILE_NAME	REGISTRATION_DATE	SAMPLE_CODE
E278537	20130111010929844-781869	false	chludwig_l110830_23_SW.mzXML.gz	2013/01/11 01:09	CHLUDWIG_L110830_23_SW
E278534	20130111023329270-781850	false	chludwig_l110830_22_SW.mzXML.gz	2013/01/10 23:33	CHLUDWIG_L110830_22_SW

Figure 6: Data selection

- New Workflow Testing Portlet:** To improve our workflows stability and to recover system setup problems as early as possible a Workflow Testing portlet was developed. This portlet provides a web service interface for submitting the same workflows that used in production. The portlet show the status of these workflow submissions and when a workflow is finished then it starts a validation. In this way we can run regular tests on our workflows.

TestWorkflow Manager

Workflow Tests Refresh

	Workflow Name	Submission Time	User	Status
▶	TPP_totetunia	12.03.2013. 17:50:42	loblum	VALIDATION_SUCCESSFUL
Validator Workflow SearchValidator on Port 0 of Job Job0 finished succesffuly				
▶	TPP_totetunia	12.03.2013. 17:18:41	loblum	VALIDATION_SUBMITTED
Validator Workflow SearchValidator on Port 0 of Job Job0 is ongoing.				

Figure 7: Testing Portlet

- Upgrade of the Workflow Monitoring Portlet:** The workflow monitor portlet was also extended to enable more advanced troubleshooting. This development enables administrators to change settings (parameters of the individual tools used in a workflow) of failed workflows and then rescue them with different parameters (re-running the workflow).

TPP-petunia	guse56test4	2013-05-22-092513	behullar	WORKFLOW_SUSPENDING	Abort Rescue Delete
TPP-petunia	guse56testB1	2013-05-22-100232	behullar	FINISHED	Abort Delete
TPP-petunia	guse56testB2	2013-05-22-100255	behullar	FINISHED	Abort Delete
TPP-petunia	guse56testB3	2013-05-22-100313	behullar	FINISHED	Abort Delete
TPP-petunia	guse56testB4	2013-05-22-100329	behullar	FINISHED	Abort Delete

Jobs Show Resource Settings

Name	Total	Ready	Running	Done	Failed	Resource Settings	Job Argument	Set
EngineSplit	5				5			<input type="checkbox"/>
Myrimatch	5					pub.1h	-i input.ini -o output.ini #n	<input type="checkbox"/>
ObisDownload	8			8		pub.1h	-i input.ini -o output.ini --PI	<input type="checkbox"/>
ObisSplit	1			1		pub.1h	-i input.ini --GENERATOR	<input type="checkbox"/>
Omssa	5					pub.1h	-i input.ini -o output.ini #n	<input type="checkbox"/>
PepProMyri	5					pub.1h	-i input.ini -o output.ini -n p	<input type="checkbox"/>
PepProOmssa	5					pub.1h	-i input.ini -o output.ini -n p	<input type="checkbox"/>
PepProTandem	5					pub.1h	-i input.ini -o output.ini -n p	<input type="checkbox"/>
Tandem	5					pub.1h	-i input.ini -o output.ini #n	<input type="checkbox"/>
Tandem2XML	5					pub.1h	-i input.ini -o output.ini #R	<input type="checkbox"/>
mz2search	5					pub.1h	-i input.ini -o output.ini #R	<input type="checkbox"/>

Figure 8: Monitoring Portlet

- New PersonalDB Portlet:** To provide more flexible and easy ways to use the system for search database registration and management we redesigned our BioDB system and added better support from the portlet side. A new portlet Personal DB Portlet was developed to enable users to upload their search databases and store them in an organized way.

Figure 9: PersonalDB Portlet

- Collaboration on the base gUSE system with JRA1:** To provide better user experience and enable our users to run large-scale analysis (like searches on hundreds of datasets) we worked also on the performance optimization of our system together with JRA1. We improved the LSF submitter component of the gUSE system with caching of job status queries to avoid overloading the cluster system and minimize the network traffic. These modifications were integrated to the official gUSE system.

Workflow updates:

- The Protein Search workflows have been consolidated. Several workflows have been incorporated into a single more generic workflow that can be parameterized in an easier manner. We have simplified the parameterization defaults, while still keeping the capability for advanced users to change all underlying settings.
- In the area of Proteomics there is currently a high interest in the new SWATH technology. Thus the workflow development was shifted from SRM and focused on a OpenSWATH based analysis workflow, together with a corresponding reference library creation workflow. Due to the integration with gUSE it is capable of processing several hundred datasets simultaneously, which is unique in the field. This now shows up as a separate 'Targeted Proteomics' workflow type in the main page of the Workflow Wizard.
- Quantification workflows have also been completely rewritten, and now the next step is to integrate them into the search workflows, performing search and quantification in one workflow.

5.2.4 iPortal Status and Plans for the Final Release

The main effort in the final development phase for iPortal will be to create a cloud-based public version of the portal. This will be a fully cloud-based portal solution, with ready-made VMs that people can also download and run on local infrastructures.

Plans for new portlets and workflows: No new portlets are planned, but we intend to improve on the existing ones based on user feedback.

- The Workflow Wizard portlet will be continuously improved depending on user feedback. We will focus on the new SWATH developments as this is now the most frequently used workflow, and here we will have most probably the need for new workflows as well.
- We will extend the Workflow Wizard also with non-proteomics workflows – one for Rosetta (structural biology) and one for Bowtie (genomics).
- BioDB and PersonalDB portlets will also be improved based on user feedback, and add features for data sharing and publication.

The detailed planning according to milestones are summarized in the table below

Task	Month	Status
WS-PGRADE dev server	M2	Done M2
Workflows form P-GRADE	M2	Done M2
Web Interface Design	M2	Done M3
Deliverable 2.1 Review	M3	Done M3
WS-PGRADE production server	M3	Done M3
Initial User Testing	M3	Done M4
TPP Workflow	M4	Done M3
Web Interface Implementation: Entry Page	M4	Done M3

Web Interface Implementation: TPP	M4	Done M3
Testing plan	M4	Done M4
LFQ Workflow	M5	Done M3
Rosetta Workflow	M6	In Progress
AAI integration	M6	Done M5
Web Interface: Update Layout	M6	Done M10
Sequest Workflow	M5	Done M5
SRM Workflow	M10	Delayed due to higher priority of the SWATH workflow, a new development that was not known when the DoW was defined.
Web Interface: Cleanup code	M10	In Progress
Workflows & Web Interface: Extend functionality	M10	Done M10
Testing Plan / Implementation	M14	Done M15
Swath + Reference Library Creation Workflow	M15	In Progress
Full Modeling Workflow	M15	
Grid access and login	M16	

5.2.5 Operation and Testing Status:

- The proteomics portal is in production and used by the lab members on a daily basis, it has more than fifty users and they have run several hundred of workflows with thousands of jobs.
- The code of the portal was integrated into the ETICS build system operated by SA2. Builds are run each week together with the implemented tests.
- Based on the operation of the server and gathered user feedback several improvements on the portal and two new portlets (workflow testing, PersonalDB) were introduced.
- The infrastructure is tested regularly using the new workflow testing portlet. This helps to detect problems within the complex infrastructure early and to react before other running workflows are affected.
- Workflow failures are monitored and our developers work together with the users on their resolution. The new portlet features greatly simplify troubleshooting with workflows.

Planning work started on the cloud integration and in the future we will work on it to provide a publicly available instance of the proteomics portal.

5.3 JRA2.3 German MoSGrid Chemist Community Science Gateway (EKUT)

MoSGrid provides access to German grid resources to enable scientists to carry out molecular simulations. The portal offers various workflows for quantum calculations, molecular dynamics and docking through specific portlets, customized to the needs of the application domains. Users are guided by multiple tutorials and help texts, as well as a user wiki and a well-curated mailing list.

5.3.1 User Feedback, Experience

Since delivery of deliverable D8.2, a series of community meetings called “MoSGrid on Tour” were carried out in Tübingen, Munich, Dortmund, Cologne and Dresden. Furthermore, MoSGrid is being used for graduate level teaching at universities in Tübingen, Munich and Cologne. In this way direct personal contact to over 100 scientists and students, working in the field of molecular simulations was possible. The general feedback was very positive, regarding the portal design, usability and concept of the MoSGrid project. From the feedback, we could identify two pertaining issues that were raised by the users: 1. The authentication is based on personal grid certificates, which is a given constraint as MoSGrid uses D-Grid infrastructure. To obtain such a certificate can be quite a hurdle for normal users, as not each German research institution has its own certificate authority. 2. The whole authentication process with obtaining a certificate, joining the virtual organization, creating a SAML assertion and finally creating a user account on the portal is perceived as being too complex. Unfortunately, the MoSGrid consortium has only little influence on these bureaucratic constraints. We are currently cooperating with NGI-DE to migrate services like the VO-management, hopefully improving some aspects of the authentication procedure.

5.3.2 Existing Setup and Features in 1st Release

The MoSGrid portal is running WS-PGRADE/gUSE 4.5.3 in combination with XtremFS as storage solution, MSML for metadata annotation and UNICORE as middleware. This setup represents a significant extension compared to a generic gUSE instance.

Regarding the 1st release the two key components for SCI-BUS, namely metadata annotation via MSML and WebGL based visualization were implemented in a basic way. This formed the technical basis for further developments.

Implemented in 1st release:

- Basic ChemDoodle support
- Basic dygraphs support
- Basic metadata annotation via MSML
- Parsing of simulation results to MSML

5.3.3 Additional Features in 2nd Release

Visualization using ChemDoodle for molecular structures and the dygraphs visualization library for displaying numerical data has been implemented in all application-specific portlets (see Figure 10).

Figure 10: A reference ligand used in a docking workflow is shown. The molecule is displayed within the Monitoring tab of the docking portlet using ChemDoodle. It is fully rotatable and different display modes can be chosen by selecting the corresponding radio buttons.

The visualization capabilities of the MoSGrid portal represent a real extra value, regarding the analysis of simulation results. Without the need of downloading any data, all relevant information about a simulation can be displayed within the portal directly.

The Molecular Markup Language (MSML) is now fully integrated in all portal and workflow components. Especially the integration of parsing nodes into all workflows provided by MoSGrid was a major endeavour. For each application and tool the conventions had to be defined for the parsing from raw output to MSML.

```

<module dictRef="compchem:finalization">
  <propertyList/>
  <molecule>
    <molecule convention="convention:molecular"
      count="11.0" id="ID15999328" cmlx:customId="0" title="ZINC18102448">
      <cmlx:customProperty key="atoms in reference ligand area">11</cmlx:customProperty>
      <cmlx:customProperty key="atoms in Pocket found by PocketDetector">0.909091</cmlx:customProperty>
      <cmlx:customProperty key="score">-10.2875</cmlx:customProperty>
      <cmlx:customProperty key="re-score">-36.2416</cmlx:customProperty>
      <atomArray atomID=" " id="ID15999328_AtomArray">
        <atom elementType="C" formalCharge="0"
          id="ID15999328_A.29045356"
          cmlx:customId="29045356" x3="3.544"
          y3="65.71" z3="64.047"/>
        <atom elementType="C" formalCharge="0"
          id="ID15999328_A.30913058"
          cmlx:customId="30913058" x3="4.49"
          y3="64.9942" z3="63.1856"/>
      </atomArray>
    </molecule>
  </molecule>
</module>
  
```

Figure 11: A small part of a MSML document is shown, which was filled to represent the input structure of a molecular docking workflow. The section shown contains information about a small molecule docked to a protein binding site. Besides information like name and identifier, docking scores, atoms and corresponding coordinates are stored.

The search functionality is currently undergoing final testing. It offers the possibility to e.g. search for a molecule identifier or display all results with a certain docking score (see Figure 11). These hits can then be used as input for further simulations.

Based on the user feedback, multiple workflows were altered or extended. Beside quantum chemical and molecular dynamics workflows, this affected in particular the docking domain. Two new applications, namely Autdock Vina and FlexX were made available and corresponding workflows exposed to the end users. This is an on-going process and we will continuously include further applications and corresponding workflows. In June 2013 we had more than 60 workflows in our gUSE repository. 21 of them are exposed to end-users through the application specific portlets.

5.3.4 Status and Plans for the Final Release

Plans for future releases

- MSML search (3rd quarter 2013)
- Editor for molecules with direct MSML annotation and repository access (4th quarter 2013)
- Docking results display combining MSML search and Chemdoodle visualization (4th quarter 2013)

5.3.5 Operation and Testing status

- Tests are up and running, thanks to excellent cooperation with 4DSoft
- Test for different browsers is working
- Test for molecule visualization is working
- Continuous implementation of further tests helping to survey all key components of the MoSGrid Portal

5.4 JRA2.4 Amsterdam Medical Centre Hospital Gateway (AMC)

The AMC hospital gateway¹ aims at facilitating data-intensive research on distributed infrastructures such as the Dutch e-science Grid and the HPC Cloud. It serves mainly biomedical researchers, but also provides a collaboration platform for interaction between these researchers and the e-science experts at the hospital.

The AMC gateway serves a user community with varied profiles in neuroscience, DNA sequencing, biostatistics, e-science and distributed computing. It provides functions to manage data and results, to start and monitor computations/workflows, and to retrieve/visualize provenance of workflow executions. Liferay social networking features (communities and user roles) are used to provide customized views for: workflow developers (with WS-PGRADE and MOTEUR workflow management systems), neuroscience researchers, bioinformaticians who perform analysis of DNA sequencing data, and the internal team – see Figure 12. Documentation is available on-line².

Figure 12: Screenshot of AMC gateway, showing list of available communities

Before the start of the SCI-BUS project, the AMC already had a gateway³ for the e-bioinfra platform⁴. This system is based on the MOTEUR workflow management engine⁵ and a few additional components, such as the DIANE pilot job framework⁶, which performs meta-scheduling on gLite resources, and the Provenance system⁷, which collects and stores information about workflow execution using the Open Provenance Model (OPM).

¹<http://www.ebioscience.amc.nl/liferay-portal-6.1.0/>

²<http://www.bioinformaticslaboratory.nl/twiki/bin/view/EBioScience/EBioInfraGatewaySCIBUS>

³<http://www.ebioscience.amc.nl/ebioinfragateway/>

⁴<http://www.bioinformaticslaboratory.nl/twiki/bin/view/EBioScience/EBioInfra>

⁵<https://nyx.unice.fr/wiki/farm/fr.unice.i3s.modalis/doku.php?id=softwares:moteur:start>

⁶<http://it-proj-diane.web.cern.ch/it-proj-diane/>

⁷Madougou et al Provenance for distributed biomedical workflow execution. Proceedings of HealthGrid, p.91-100,2012

The goal of the AMC in SCI-BUS is to port this gateway completely to the WS-PGRADE platform, converting the workflows to WS-PGrade and the web applications into LifeRay portlets. So far, a big part of this objective has been realized, as described later. Currently, both the MOTEUR and the WS-PGrade platforms co-exist under the same Liferay container, and the user can change from one view to the other. The grid security and file management portlets are shared by both interfaces for workflow developers. A set of simple portlets has been developed to interface with the legacy e-bioinfra services.

Additionally, the intention is to develop customized user interfaces for each of the various groups of users at the AMC. The first application-specific Neuroscience gateway (NSG) to be developed provides neuroscientists easy access to both data sources and high-performance computing resources in order to perform applications like brain image analysis (for example, Freesurfer application for brain segmentation and DTI pre-processing and brain fibers tracking). Additional gateways for Exome sequencing and Protein Docking are also considered for the last project year.

5.4.1 User Feedback and Experience

The WS-PGRADE/gUSE portal is in use within our community since 2012. We have had several positive and some negative experiences in workflow development, as well as in the maintenance of the portal. These experiences are summarized at the end of this section.

Recently, we finished the development of the neuroscience gateway (NSG), which will become operational in the coming days (expected to be released for beta users in mid July 2013). Therefore, there is so far no feedback available from the end-users of the NS gateway (i.e., neuroscientists).

One of the advantages of the gUSE framework is its ability to send the jobs to various DCIs. For a workflow developer, this is a very handy feature because it has facilitated changing the target DCI for job execution, thanks to the so-called DCI Bridge. Nevertheless, our administrators would like to have more control on DCI Bridge, e.g., to be able to (1) enable/disable various back-ends for individual users, (2) run “local” tasks as a restricted user, (3) blacklist resources to avoid unreliable compute nodes, (4) more information for troubleshooting, etc. We hope that such requirements will be taken into account in due time, as we have seen that other requests, such as robot certificates for job submission, have already been implemented in JRA1.

A complementary feature to DCI Bridge is the new promised gUSE development called “Data Bridge”. Most of the workflows developed on our site need to handle large files (in the order of GB). In terms of a workflow, it means that the transfer of these files between jobs needs to be optimized, i.e., it cannot go through the portal server. This feature would be the main characteristic of the upcoming “Data bridge” which we welcome and look forward to.

The graphical user interface of gUSE speeds up the development of workflows, as it provides much functionality in a user-friendly manner. Nevertheless, this user interface has quite some room for improvement. In the course of time, the number of clicks required to do some tasks becomes unmanageably large leading to errors and user frustration. To remedy this, some of our users have developed some command-line workarounds to their repetitive tasks. Furthermore, with all the different aspects that gUSE should handle, the set of error scenarios handled by the portal is limited. Many times workflow submissions (or other parts of the system) fail with no proper error message. Another aspect is the graph editor, which currently runs as a Java web start application. It would be better if this interface would also be implemented within the browser.

In workflow development, despite the advantages of WS-PGRADE, there are many points that increase the error-proneness of development and execution. For example, setting lfn (logical file name) of a remote input/output is done by typing the lfn as a string. A small typing mistake here is caught only after the workflow is submitted, queued in the grid, and has started executing. Similarly, in order to pass the “internal name” of a port as a parameter (or worse to hardcode it in the script), one should just retype it. One solution is to specify the inputs as independent entities, which can, on the one hand, be assigned to multiple workflows/components if necessary, and, on the other hand, be used directly as input parameters to the executable of a component.

Despite its comprehensive functionality, WS-PGRADE is still missing some features or has no easy way to handle some common problems. Here is a representative list of problems we have encountered, which we have communicated to the gUSE developers for further improvement:

- Keep the extension of an input file in the internal name: The internal job may depend on the type of the input file, which is usually understood from the extension.
 - A possible solution: add an ASM method that can update the internal name of a port and adjust the extension.
- Grid proxy is created by gUse for 12 hours and expires before a long job completes
- Change the default for the parameter sweep was a "cross" instead of a "dot" product:
 - because this is used most
 - because there are more possibilities that way

Finally, we remark that we have made several bug reports, some of which are already resolved during upgrades of gUSE. Two examples of still open reports include:

- Persistence of information: <https://sourceforge.net/p/guse/bugs/32/>
- Workflows disappear after restart: <https://sourceforge.net/p/guse/bugs/87/>

5.4.2 Previous status in 1st Release

In the first release of the AMC e-bioinfra gateway the target user community was workflow developers of both the MOTEUR and WS-PGRADE systems. The system was configured to support computing on gLite resources, and also the user pages and general website organization were planned. The portal was available for internal testing only.

The following portlets were added to the generic WS-PGRADE distribution (more details about these portlets, with screenshots can be found in D8.2):

- MOTEUR portlet: implements dashboard to monitor status of execution of MOTEUR workflows (legacy workflow management engine)
- Provenance portlet: a Provenance collector system was developed for MOTEUR workflows. The collected data is stored in a database using the Open Provenance Model (OPM). This portlet provides user interface to query, explore and visualize Provenance of the workflow executions.

At that time only test workflows were available in the portal repository.

Note: due to manpower problems, the customized interface for the neuroscience users was not yet implemented in the first release.

5.4.3 Additional Developments in 2nd Release

The second release of the gateway included the following improvements

- a new release of WP-PGRADE was re-installed from scratch
- new theming was applied to Liferay to provide visual identity to the AMC e-bioinfra (see Figure 14)
- two local clusters were added to the DCI Bridge
- new groups and user pages were designed for courses (bachelor and graduate levels)
- a new portlet was developed to implement the customized services and interface for the neuroscience community of the AMC
- development of several workflows implementing neuroimaging, DNA sequencing and protein docking applications.

The following sections describe in some details the major development achieved within the second release, namely the so called NeuroScience Gateway (NSG) portlet and the application workflows.

The NeuroScience Gateway (NSG) portlet has been developed mainly targeting the Neuroscience community. The NSG portlet has been built in a generic way so that it can be adapted for other application domains. Figure 13 presents an overview of the Portlet components, which include: viewer, e-bioinfra metadata catalogue (eCAT); a processing manager (PM) and a data transport service (DTS).

Figure 13: Overview of the main NSG components including the viewer, metadata catalogue, the processing manager and the Data Transport Service.

5.4.3.1 Viewer

The web interface with the user is implemented by the Viewer component. It queries the catalogue to populate in user-friendly forms that present metadata about the various objects that the user can manipulate in the gateway: data, metadata and processing experiments.

The user can filter the objects on different metadata. Figure 14 below shows a screenshot of the gateway.

Figure 14: NSG Viewer showing the monitoring interface for processing tasks started with the gateway

5.4.3.2 e-bioinfra Metadata catalogue (eCAT)

We observed that at the AMC every group of researchers (e.g. neuroscientist or human geneticists) has its own procedure to implement rules and regulations regarding the storage and protection of biomedical research data, as well as policies for data sharing and archiving. So it would be inefficient, and possibly not even allowed, to duplicate the data resource at the gateway server. Therefore, we decided to rely on existing, external, biomedical research data and metadata resources, as well as on their own security mechanisms and policies. In the case of Neuroscience, XNAT⁸ has been selected as main source of data, image metadata and access control. The data server is connected to the e-BioInfra Gateway by agreement

⁸ The eXtensible Neuroimaging Archive Toolkit (XNAT): <http://www.xnat.org>

between the neuroscience user community and the gateway providers, and the data becomes available for processing at the gateway for authorized users only.

The eCAT links the data sources with the compute resources. It keeps metadata (provenance) about workflow execution, data replicas on the DCI and user preferences, and application domain-specific information. The data in eCAT is organized as illustrated in Figure 15 below.

Figure 15: a simplified view of the eCAT data model

5.4.3.3 Processing manager

The Processing Manager (PM) takes care of submission and monitoring of data processing applications, which are defined as workflows executed by the gUSE Workflow Interpreter. The PM instructs the data transport service to copy input files from the data resource to the storage resources of the DCI on which the processing is performed. It also starts the copy of results generated by the jobs back to the data resource with the proper metadata. The PM imports the workflow from the gUSE Application Repository and configures it with the physical location of input data before submission.

5.4.3.4 Data transport service

The Data Transport Service (DTS) transfer data between the domain-specific data servers and the storage resources on DCIs. This service contacts the eCAT to determine how to authenticate the IMS on behalf of the user, how to authenticate with the storage resources of the DCI (possibly with community credentials), and how to access data on both. It autonomously performs the data transfer using third-party mechanisms as much as possible to avoid bottlenecks. If some data has been replicated on a DCI, the location of that replica is stored in the eCAT and retrieved later.

The Data Transport Service (DTS) transports data between IMSs and storage resources on DCIs. This service contacts the eCAT to determine how to authenticate the IMS on behalf of the user, how to authenticate with the storage resources of the DCI (possibly with community credentials), and how to access data on both. It autonomously performs the data transfer using third-party mechanisms as much as possible to avoid bottlenecks. If some data has been replicated on a DCI, the location of that replica is stored in the eCAT and retrieved later.

5.4.3.5 New Workflows

With the introduction of WS-PGRADE as web-based environment for workflow development and executions, more advanced users became workflow developers. The legacy applications are being ported to WS-PGRADE platform are summarized below, including the ongoing workflows:

Application	Application domain	Workflow implementation
Vina Autodock	Molecular docking	ongoing
Double cross validation	Mass spectrometry	ready
Freesurfer	Neuroimaging	ready
SNP Annotation	DNA sequencing	ready
SNP Calling	DNA sequencing	ready
Sequence Alignment	DNA sequencing	ongoing
Indel Calling	DNA sequencing	ongoing
Sequence Assembly of small genomes	DNA sequencing	ongoing
Simulation of low coverage sequencing	DNA sequencing	ready
Exome sequencing	DNA sequencing	ongoing
DTI pre-processing	Neuroimaging	ready
BedpostX	Neuroimaging	ongoing

5.4.4 Status and Plans

The releases of the AMC e-Bioinfra gateway have been historically delayed due to manpower problems in the first project year. The development of the customized gateway for neurosciences actually only restarted in November 2012, and since then, most of the deferred tasks have been accomplished. The generic gateway has been used by beta users, namely internal members of the e-bioscience development team and advanced users who closely collaborate with the development team in DNA sequencing, Neuroscience and Metabolomics applications. The system has been used also for practical exercises in two courses for AMC students in Medical Informatics and Biomedicine respectively at undergraduate and graduate levels.

The neuroscience gateway will soon enable the use of medical imaging applications by neuroscientists directly. We will add additional applications and evaluate it in the third project year.

Additionally, a prototype for Exome Sequencing is being designed based on the same basic components of the NSG portlet. Since this portlet was designed to provide more generic functionality, we expect that this portlet can be reused or adapted to support this new application domain by customizing the data services, workflows and Viewer.

Task	Month	Status
Operational gateway version 3.4	M8	done M8

configuration of the gateway for the Dutch grid resources using VLEMED VO	M8	done M8
Definition of communities for the various user profiles	M8	done M6
simple portlets to access the e-bioinfra legacy services (workflow dashboard and provenance retrieval)	M11	done M11
WS-PGRADE/gUSE re-install/upgrade (from 3.4 to 3.5.2) on production server	M14	done M15
Design NSG (and refining in multiple Agile iterations)	M8	done M15
WS-PGRADE/gUSE reinstall/upgrade + portal and legacy portlets migration/configuration on production server	M15	done M15
Complete Implementation of NSG portlet	M21	M22
Test server with virtualization and Virtual Machine install and configurable (WS_PGRADE/gUSE version 3.5.2)	M18	M18
User Acceptance release/tests (UAT) on Test Server iterations	M21	delayed (will start M23)
NSG becomes operational	M21	In progress. Target M22
Validate and improve NSG user interface	M28	
Add new applications to the NSG	M28	
Design and implement prototype for DNA sequencing gateway based on NSG	M30	
Design, implement and evaluate prototype for protein docking gateway based on ASM directly	M29	
Support for cloud back-end in the AMC gateway	M22	Discontinued. There is no support in gUse for the middleware used by the Dutch HPC cloud.
Final gateway release and evaluation for all AMC user communities (neuro, DNA Seq, biochem)	M34	

5.4.5 Operation and Testing status

We use Virtual machines for development and integration testing, When the system is satisfactorily tested, it is migrated to the production server, where user testing and satisfaction is carried on the production server.

5.5 JRA2.5 PireGrid Community Commercial Gateway (UNIZAR-BIFI)

The PireGrid Community Commercial Gateway is a generic purpose gateway that intends to facilitate the use of the computing resources allocated at UNIZAR-BIFI for companies, researchers and users.

The need to create a gateway appeared within the context of the PireGrid project. It was aimed to introduce companies, especially SMEs, to distributed computing, and some applications were adapted to Grid. During the PireGrid project, some demos and presentations were made, fact that awoke the interest of some companies. By that time, Cloud technologies were becoming more and more used. Some of these companies were also using Hadoop, a well-known map-reduce implementation to analyse data and solve key-value pair algorithms.

Due to these requirements, and knowing that the problem of this kind of distributed infrastructures is that sometimes they are difficult to use for non-experienced users, we have developed our portal as an easy way to access Hadoop as SaaS over our cloud infrastructure, adapting the existing WS-PGRADE developments.

Apart from the Grid functionalities of WS-PGRADE, the main new features of this portal are:

- Friendly interface for Hadoop job for creation, execution and monitoring
- Hadoop application customization
- Cloud infrastructure management
- Cloud storage support integrated in the interface

The gateway is public and accessible from the URL <http://gateway.bifi.unizar.es>. The architecture of the gateway can be observed in the following figure:

Figure 16: Gateway Architecture

5.5.1 User Feedback, Experience

Once the first portal release was deployed and published, our users community started using it and giving us feedback. This community has been continuously growing, and new applications have been run using this gateway. New companies, and even different research groups, have tested this environment. We also prepared some sessions in which we explained the SCI-BUS project, the portal features, and how it works, showing some practical examples. Putting together all the feedback we gathered, we can summarize what we realized it should be improved or added in the following points:

- Support for larger jobs in storage. In the first release, files were uploaded directly from the user machine to the gateway server, and then from there to the cloud resources for each job. This situation was not efficient, especially for big amounts of data. The bandwidth needed was too high, and the server was significantly overloaded. This way, we realized we had to provide an alternative for storing files
- Stability was not perfect, especially for complex jobs that used a lot of external libraries. Some users reported that this kind of jobs failed randomly. Some further problems appeared. They were related to the virtual infrastructure that were causing problems freezing VMs
- Statistical information about the use of the gateway should be added, at least to allow us to provide a better service, knowing how the system was used, and registering exactly where problems were happening.

5.5.2 Existing Setup and Features in 1st Release

BifiUnizar gateway is a general-purpose gateway. It takes advantage of all Liferay features for managing users, managing communities, customizing the appearance, etc., and it uses all the WS-PGRADE functionalities to access our AraGrid resource, connected via the gLite DCI Bridge that gUSE provides.

For the first release, the following features documented in D8.2 were developed:

- Access to the AraGRID infrastructure through WS-PGRADE portlets
- Access to our OpenStack Cloud infrastructure to run Hadoop jobs using a specifically developed Hadoop portlet. The OpenStack version deployed in the first version was Essex. This first version of the Hadoop portlet had the following functionalities:
 - A single new workflow that allows to submit and run new Hadoop jobs on our Cloud infrastructure. In this first version, only simple jobs were supported, and advanced features such as customization of the infrastructure resources or use of external libraries were not supported because of the complexity they presented.
 - Job monitoring and history. Users were able to list running and already finished Hadoop jobs. They could check their status, retrieve the results when

terminated, and look at the execution log for possible errors if they were reported.

- Input/output management. Files used in the job execution could be just transferred to the infrastructure uploading/downloading them directly from/to the server.

The virtual infrastructure currently used in Hadoop jobs can be appreciated in the following figure:

Figure 17: Current virtual infrastructure used in Hadoop

5.5.3 Additional Features in 2nd Release

Taking into account the user feedback mentioned before that we collected thanks to the experience of the first release, the following features were added to the first release of the gateway:

- The OpenStack infrastructure was upgraded from the Essex version to the Folsom version. It introduced a lot of new features, the most important ones for our portal were:
 - This release had a special focus on ease of use, performance, and security, allowing also the customization of large pools of virtual machines.
 - Support for OpenStack Object Storage (SWIFT), with which operators are able to connect OpenStack Object Storage to a statsd server and receive

hundreds of real-time metrics about their cluster to help with troubleshooting, diagnostics, day-to-day operational issues, and long-term capacity management.

- Improved OpenStack Dashboard, called Horizon, that brings usability improvements in launching compute instances, working Object Storage resources, and managing OpenStack projects and users. It includes support for public and private image uploads and management of advanced networks.
 - A new API, a new client library, and new replication options were introduced to the Image Service for increased performance and security improvements reaching from the client to the image storage.
- The OpenStack Java SDK used in the Hadoop portlet to access the infrastructures was also upgraded to the latest version in order to make it work with the new OpenStack release, to correct bugs, and to benefit from all the improvements this version was offering. This implied lots of changes in the API, so the developed Hadoop portlet had to be significantly redesigned.
 - Taking advantage of this redesign, the Hadoop portlet was upgraded to make it work with newer versions of WS-PGRADE/Liferay. This had to be done because we tested it and it did not work out of the box, so we decided to upgrade and redeploy it in order to benefit from all the new features WS-PGRADE 3.5.6/Liferay 6.1 provided.
 - The single workflow of the Hadoop portlet has been preserved in order to keep usability, but it has been improved to support more complex Hadoop jobs that use external libraries, to allow to customize the computing resources of the VMs that will be used during the execution, and to support a new storage alternative.
 - Support for OpenStack SWIFT was added as a storage alternative. It involved some problems that had to be solved. For example, it appeared an issue using large files that provoked excesses in the heap limit. To solve it and to improve stability, we finally had to include native SWIFT commands.
 - In this new Hadoop portlet version a unique OpenStack project is used to run all different jobs in order to allow us to get statistics maintaining transparency for users.
 - Monitoring and statistics features have been added to the existing Hadoop portlet, and we are currently developing charts to show them in a graphical way to users.

In **Figure 18** we can see the main use case of the portal using the new SWIFT features added.

Figure 18: SWIFT use case

Figure 19: Screenshot of the SWIFT container tab of the portlet

Hadoop Portlet Architecture

The portlet architecture has been slightly modified during the second year of development. It has three main components:

- The web interface: it provides transparent access for users to all the features the portlet provides. It is divided in four different tabs:
 - The first one, called “Submit Job”, already existed in the first release, and allows to create a new job, assigning it a name and uploading the JAR and input files. In the new version it allows to indicate the external libraries and the parameters that the job will use, but also allows to configure the virtual infrastructure that will be used for the job execution.
 - The second one, called “Job status” also existed in the first release, and it lists all the jobs that the user has executed using this portlet.
 - The third tab, “Import Data”, is new, and it allows to upload input files directly to the OpenStack infrastructure, saving time and server resources.
 - The fourth tab, “Containers List” is also new in this release, and it allows managing the user SWIFT resources and files.
- The server, that has installed Liferay 6.1 and WS-PGRADE 3.5.6, and in which the Hadoop portlet is deployed. It is the intermediary between users and the infrastructure, and it is in charge of communicating them in order to run Hadoop jobs

as the user requests. For this, it transforms user interaction in a set of commands that are sent to the OpenStack Manager that we have developed. The server also saves all the relevant information in a local database that helps users to know what is happening in the system.

- The OpenStack Manager, is a library that directly connects to the OpenStack infrastructure. It manages the virtual resources and the needed files to run the job in the virtual infrastructure and to retrieve the results correctly to the user.

Figure 20: Hadoop portlet architecture

Hadoop submit job sequence

Running a Hadoop job for non-experienced users can be difficult, and with our Hadoop portlet, we have tried to transfer this difficulty to the MapReduce server making it as simple as possible. Submitting a new job consist of filling a simple form indication the job name, the JAR and input files, the parameters of the job, and the number and kind of VMs that we want to use. The server will take care of everything else transparently: connect to the infrastructure, authenticate, check the available resources, create the instances, assign them IPs, upload the files to the infrastructure, start the execution, check its status while it is running, retrieve the results when it has finished, show the errors if they have appeared,

delete the instances when everything has finished, free the used IPs to reuse them in the future, etc. None of this operations is performed by the user, he just fills a form, clicks on run, and waits for the results to be presented in the web interface.

The full sequence can be seen in **Figure 21**.

Figure 21: Submit Hadoop job sequence

OpenStack management

Once the user has submitted a new job, several operations and checks are performed for setting up the virtual infrastructure and running it.

In **Figure 22** we can see the sequence performed when deploying a new job. When all the instances have been properly deployed and the needed files have been copied, the Hadoop command is run. When it finishes, results are retrieved, and the virtual infrastructure is disassembled and freed to be reused by new submitted jobs.

Figure 22: Hadoop job deployment

5.5.4 Status and Plans

Currently, the status of the gateway can be summarized in the following points:

- The second release of the portal is in production, and our community is using it every day. We have already dozens of users and hundreds of run jobs.
- Some important improvements have been developed based on users feedback. New features have been also added in order to get a better user experience and to make the portal more operable.
- The infrastructure has been upgraded and balanced efficiently, what improves stability, performance and reliability.
- The code has been restructured and ported to the new version of Liferay/WS-PGRADE. Tests are run successfully every week.

The main development work has been successfully finished, and as a result, the gateway is currently public and fully accessible. We have in mind some minor improvements that we will work in the coming months. Two of the most important ones are including charts to present users usage statistics (users have requested this feature, and we think that it will be also useful for admins), and improving the graphical appearance of the portal in order to make it more attractive, but our efforts are going to focus in getting more and more users.

In this table we can find the main tasks that have been planned for this project and the status in which currently they are:

Task	Month	Status
Requeriments collection for portal adaption	M3	Done M3
gUSE and WS-PGRADE installation	M4	Done M4
Web Interface Design	M4	Done M4
Portal prototype	M6	Done M6
Interface implementation	M7	Done M8
API for Hadoop implementation	M8	Done M10
Infrastructure integration	M10	Done M12
Interface tests	M7	Done M13
Hadoop API tests	M9	Done M13
Global tests	M12	Done M18
WS-PGRADE production server	M12	Done M12
Infrastructute upgrade		Done M18
Portlet internal redesign		Done M19
Support for OpenStack SWIFT		Done M19
Statistics and monitoring information		Done M19
Statistics charts, accounting		
Gateway general appearance		

5.5.5 Operation and Testing Status

The BifiUnizar gateway is currently in production, and it has a community of around 40 active users. Just one workflow is available that makes possible to run all kind of Hadoop jobs. Currently around one thousand jobs have been run.

There has been developed together with SA2 a main test that checks all the principal Hadoop functionalities of the portal. It is run every week and it reports by email if some problem has been encountered. For the moment no error has been found.

All the problems are monitored so our admin and development team solves them as soon as possible. Logs, input/output and program files are saved in order to be able to reproduce the errors and study them, because sometimes they are very complex.

We have carried out some performance tests and we have obtained very good results. In the following chart we can see how a single job can be run using considerably less time, reaching more than half the original time depending on the virtual resources used. The chart test in **Figure 23** has been performed for a benchmark program called Terasort that measures the time to sort 20GB of randomly generated data.

Figure 23: Performance comparison for the same Terasort job in different architectures using different number of nodes.

You can find more information and screenshots about the Hadoop portlet in the user guide that is public and accessible from the following URL:

<http://gateway.bifi.unizar.es/documents/10180/f00123c3-dc43-454c-9986-4d5757022541>

5.6 JRA2.6 Commercial Gateway for Business Process Optimization (SIMSOFT)

The SimBusPro portal was developed to help optimize Business Processes by simulating them in the SCI-BUS framework. By simulating a large number of business processes in a distributed Grid/Cloud environment the user can identify the differences between them easily by analysing visualized reports. All Business Processes that are modelled with a BPMN2 editor can be simulated using our gateway.

The SimBusPro portal has two types of user. First type is administrator user who is responsible of setup and maintaining the portal. He has access to all pages including WSPGRADE interfaces and SimBusPro portal custom admin pages. Administrator user uses WSPGRADE interfaces for setting gUSE services and uses the custom admin pages for adjusting custom SimBusPro Portal settings .The second type is end user type who has only access to easy user interfaces of SimBusPro portal which only exploit the main business process logic.The SimBusPro public portal runs at <http://simbuspro.com/liferay-portal-6.1.0/> since January 2013.

All core functionalities of the gateway have been implemented. These are:

- Integration with business process model editor tool
- Importing business process models manually
- Producing business process alternatives
- Simulation on a Distributed Computed Infrastructure
- Generating visualized report with graphs and charts

5.6.1 User Feedback, Experience

We have worked with several partners including University of Gazi and University of Bilkent (for more information D8.3 Part 5.6) to utilize our gateway during the prototype and production phase. During these collaborations, we have collected feedbacks from our partners and have chosen the most relevant and significant requests and implemented them. We also have solved the problems that users have encountered.

Here is the list showing the reported issues and requests for improvement by our users.

- Reports created after simulation of alternative models should be more simple and informative. For example, only best, worst and average models should be displayed in terms of cost.
- With the new release in January of 2013, there were report creation problems that could occur randomly. The problem was due to the new portal environment, Liferay 6.1.0. In previous releases that have used Liferay version 6.0.5, there was no such problem.
- When producing alternative module, new models should be generated based on process parameters.
- When big numbers of jobs (~1000 jobs) are sent, performance decreases dramatically.

- SimBusPro Portal uses only one workflow for gUSE interactions. Administrators can create test workflows for portal and they would like to select the active workflow for SimBusPro Portal. In first release the portal has used the default Liferay theme so users wanted to work with more sophisticated theme for portal.

5.6.2 Existing Setup and Features in 1st Release

SimBusPro Gateway v1.0.0 was released in October 2012. With some revision and improvement, v1.3.0 was released in January 2013. These first releases included the following features:

- Single or multiple models can be imported into portal
- Imported models are simulated on the DCI.
- Simulation report is generated for a single model
- Simulation report is generated for a group of models
- Alternative models are produced from a base model that was imported by the user.

5.6.3 Additional Features in 2nd Release

Based on user feedbacks and our plans, we have added the following features to the gateway:

- A new user interface was designed and implemented for the gateway.
- The WS-PGRADE/gUSE environment used by the gateway was upgraded to version 3.5.1
- The Report module has been improved according to user feedbacks. For alternative models, the simulation report does not include results of all models, but only specific ones with regard to cost groups (3 groups of models are given in reports: best cost, worst cost and average cost). This grouping provides a better overview to the user, compared to other systems.
- Report creation problems occurred due to the new version Liferay Portal in version 6.1.0. We fixed the problem as soon as we were informed.
- Administrators can select the active workflow for SimBusPro Portal.
- The functionality of producing alternatives for Imported Business Models has been revised and improved. Previously, users could produce alternative models based on resource data of business processes. With the new improvement the user additionally can enter range for process parameters, see **Figure 24**.

The screenshot shows the SimBus Pro interface with the SimBusProGateway window open. The window displays a table of process parameters with columns for Parameter Type, Parameter Name, Parameter Value, Parameter Range, Parameter Range Min, Parameter Range Max, and Parameter Range Interval. A 'PRODUCE ALTERNATIVE' button is visible at the top left of the table area.

PARAMETER TYPE	PARAMETER NAME	PARAMETER VALUE	PARAMETER RANGE	PARAMETER RANGE MIN	PARAMETER RANGE MAX	PARAMETER RANGE INTERVAL
ProcessParams	cimento_sureci - komur	200	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	10	50	5
ProcessParams	cimento_sureci - kil	250	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	50	75	1
ProcessParams	cimento_sureci - kalker	10	<input type="checkbox"/>			
ProcessParams	cimento_sureci - alci_tasi	10	<input type="checkbox"/>			
ProcessParams	cimento_sureci - kum	10	<input type="checkbox"/>			
ProcessParams	cimento_sureci - kkk_bileseni	15	<input type="checkbox"/>			
ProcessParams	cimento_sureci - kkk_bileseni	15	<input type="checkbox"/>			
ProcessParams	cimento_sureci - kkkta_bileseni	15	<input type="checkbox"/>			
ProcessParams	cimento_sureci - tras	10	<input type="checkbox"/>			
ProcessParams	cimento_sureci - kul	10	<input type="checkbox"/>			
ProcessParams	cimento_sureci - dokme_cimento	15	<input type="checkbox"/>			
ProcessParams	cimento_sureci - torbali_cimento	15	<input type="checkbox"/>			
SimResource	kontrolor_insan - quantity	1	<input type="checkbox"/>			
SimResource	kontrolor_insan - fixedCost	0.0	<input type="checkbox"/>			
SimResource	kontrolor_insan - timeCost	0.0	<input type="checkbox"/>			
SimResource	baski_makinesi - quantity	1	<input type="checkbox"/>			
SimResource	baski_makinesi - fixedCost	0.0	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	1000	100000	5000
SimResource	baski_makinesi - timeCost	0.0	<input type="checkbox"/>			
SimResource	stokhol - quantity	1	<input type="checkbox"/>			
SimResource	stokhol - fixedCost	0.0	<input type="checkbox"/>			
SimResource	stokhol - timeCost	0.0	<input type="checkbox"/>			
SimResource	gumus - quantity	1	<input type="checkbox"/>			
SimResource	gumus - fixedCost	0.0	<input type="checkbox"/>			
SimResource	gumus - timeCost	0.0	<input type="checkbox"/>			
SimResource	milled_coal_silo - quantity	1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	1	4	1

Figure 24: Selection of Process Parameters

The screenshot shows the SimBus Pro interface with the SimBusProGateway window open. The window displays a 'Back' button, the active workflow name 'wf2', and a dropdown menu for selecting workflows. A 'List Workflows from repository' button is also present. Below, a table lists available workflows for selection.

Active Workflow Name: wf2, Owner Name: 10196

Get workflows from: 10196 [List Workflows from repository](#)

Selected Owner is : 10196

Select	Workflow Name	Workflow Type
<input checked="" type="radio"/>	wf1	appl
<input type="radio"/>	wf2	appl

[Set Active Workflow](#)

Powered By Liferay

Figure 25: Administrators can select active workflow from multiple workflows they have used in the system

Figure 26: User Forum

Figure 27: User Guide

Figure 28: Video Tutorial

5.6.4 SimBusPro Status and Plans

- The SimBusPro portal is in production since January of 2013 and has 10 users.
- Our users have been actively giving feedback that provides opportunities to improve our portal.
- All core functionalities of the SimBusPro portal were implemented.
- The new user interface of the portal was designed and implemented.
- We currently continue to work on the third real business process model (service route). In this project, we collaborate with Bilkent University to improve it.
- We still continue negotiating with an iron casting plant. We are at preparation level to begin a simulation project.

We continue to improve the simulation engine and the report module according to user feedback.

Task	Month	Status
Preparation of SRS	M2	Done M2
Installing of gUSE& WS-PGRADE	M2	Done M2

Installation of 3G-Bridge	M2	Done M2
Installing of Local Desktop Grid	M2	Done M2
Integration with gUSE and Desktop Grid	M3	Done M4
First Real Business Process Model (Tempered Glass Production)	M4	Done M4
Second Real Business Process Model (Cement Production)	M4	Done M4
Preparation of Test Plan	M4	Done M4
The functionality of Uploading and Simulating User Inputs	M5	Done M6
The functionality of Viewing Result Report for one input	M6	Done M6
Simulation Outputs will be Migrated into Main Database of Portlet	M7	Done M8
The functionality of Viewing Result Report for Multiple Input	M8	Done M8
Parsing and Saving of User inputs within Gateway	M9	Done M9
Detail Test Cases	M9	Done M9
SA2 Integration	M9	Done M14
The functionality of Producing Alternatives for Imported Business Process Model	M10	Done M14
New Web Interface Implemented	M10	Done M14
Migrate the newer gUSE version	M11	Done M14
Setup of Production environment	M11	Done M10
Third Real Business Process Model (Service Route)	M22	In Progress
Web Interface Enhancement	M24	In Progress
Improving in terms of Usability	M24	In Progress

5.6.5 Operation and Testing Status

SimBusPro was integrated with 4D ETICS Portal with regard to SA2. All tests are implemented and run periodically. Currently we run 12 tests for the gateway. When new functional components are added, corresponding tests for them will be added to this group too.

5.7 JRA2.7 Blender Rendering Community Gateway (LU)

Renderfarm.fi (the Blender Rendering Community Gateway) is the world's largest and most popular volunteer computing based rendering platform (the service currently has over 10 000 registered users who all have the potential to send a rendering task to the service). The rendering service technology is based on BOINC (Berkeley Open Infrastructure for Network Computing) and BURP (Big and Ugly Rendering Project) and Blender, the world's most popular open source 3D suite. During SCI-BUS Renderfarm.fi is being stabilized it's platforms are being virtualized. Also the functions and usable scenarios are being extended by extending the system with a bridge to WS-PGRADE/gUSE technology.

5.7.1 User Feedback, Experience

Initial user feedback received through Renderfarm.fi's service forums and social media was extremely positive after the implementation of the Blender Cycles rendering engine, which increased the workload of the service by over 100% and quickly resulted in over 5000 new registered users on the service. Further user feedback will be collected upon the finishing of the new gateway frontend during 2013. The new frontend is still being improved.

5.7.2 Existing Setup and Features in 1st Release

The initial state of the Renderfarm.fi project at the beginning of SCI-BUS was a mostly functioning Gentoo Linux based service, which had serious problems with scalability. The development was done directly in the production environment. Though there were several thousand registered users on the service, the amount of computations was well below the capacity of the volunteer network.

M1-M3: In the first three months (M1-M3) Laurea focused on creating a virtualized development environment (Virtualbox based), in which work can progress with gUSE and the remote API without jeopardizing the production environment.

M4-M6: The next three months (M4-M6) Laurea continued to expand on the functionality of the Renderfarm.fi gateway. The main development focus was shifted to the integration of the Cycles ray-tracer rendering engine, which was introduced in to Blender at this point. This was done due to the impressive increase in demand for rendering power directly tied to the computing heavy ray-tracer.

M7-M9: The development focus during this period was on continuing the integration of the Cycles rendering engine and on stabilising the service, namely to heighten the service level provided to users. New features created during this period include a new type of work unit validator (implemented, feature works by simulating the human visual system) as well as the ability to prioritize certain renders over others.

M10-12: Laurea continued on the Cycles integration as well extending Blender with PySpaces support (for a more general solution to integrating the Renderfarm.fi Uploader – the only method for users to input work to the gateway) as well as extending the existing XMLRPC API in order to move away from an old and unnecessarily bulky Java-PHP bridge.

Extensions to making the service more operation capable (including the development of a "jam handler", "stage queue" and "cleanup handler" have also taken place). Initial

development of the gUSE extension and gUSE client also took place, however this never advanced to a testing state due to a full server crash that happened in M12 (see 5.7.3 for more).

In hindsight, the integration of Cycles into the service made an immediate impact as the usage and amount of registered users tripled in a just few months, when compared to the pre-Cycles era. Though the gUSE integration was not completed as originally planned, the overall scalability – and ultimately the maintainability of the project in the long term (post-SCI-BUS) – of the service was extremely positively affected by the developments done for the 1st release.

5.7.3 Additional Features in 2nd Release

Work on the extending parts was pushed back because of a severe server crash (M12) and the eventual decision to do a full server virtualization. Although server virtualization (and move from a Gentoo Linux to a Debian based installation) was largely finished (M14), the stabilizing of the environment proved extremely challenging and took much longer than expected. The most recent indications (June 2013) give reason to believe that this work has now been successfully completed. After migrating the service from Virtual Box to a KVM based virtual machine, it has been running stable for two weeks.

The crash and eventual work on the virtualization of services resulted in a lengthy (more than two months) halt to the service, creating a long queue of work from users that is still being resolved. The new functionality (linking to the MTA SZTAKI grid via a gUSE Remote API client/bridge for a fluid simulation workflow as detailed in D8.2) has been finished, but has not been fully tested. LU expects to finish these tests before the end of September 2013.

A new gateway frontend was also established and work on it is expected to be finished in August 2013. This frontend is not based on Liferay as it was decided that the target user community differs immensely from the average SCI-BUS community (ie. scientists versus citizen scientists). This decision approved by the consortium prior to its execution. All frontend related work has been developed at Laurea’s expense (no commitment from SCI-BUS budget), but is still tightly aligned with Laurea’s commitment to the SCI-BUS deliverables.

5.7.4 Blender Rendering Community Gateway Status and Plans

Task	Month	Status
gUSE installation	M2	Done M2
Cycles renderer support	M6	Done M6
BURP features	M7	Done M7
BURP gUSE Manager	M9	Done M9
BURP stabilization	M11	Done M11
Uploader improvements	M12	Done M12
Server virtualization	M14	Done M14
Gateway frontend improvement 1/2	M14	Done M14
Extending the XMLRPC API	M17	Done M16
Server stabilization	M21	Done M20
gUSE extension + client	M21	Delayed

Gateway frontend improvement 2/2	M21	In progress
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5.7.5 Blender Rendering Community Status and Plans for Final Release

The final release of the Blender Rendering Gateway is a fully virtualized, scalable, professional level rendering solution that can be easily installed on any KVM capable platform. The final release not only introduces integration with Cycles (Blender's new ray-tracing based rendering engine), but also offers a newly developed second workflow for doing separate fluid simulation passes on a partner's network. This workflow is built on top of the gUSE Remote API.

Most of the intended work has now been completed, with additional work on stabilizing of the server completed during June 2013. Work on gUSE Remote API is expected to complete M22.

5.7.6 Operation and Testing Status

Unit tests have been written and completed during M18, but the test suite hasn't been installed on the testing partner infrastructure yet. Laurea expects to have this completed by M22.

With the stabilization of the server in M20, Laurea can focus on continuing the operation of the service as per normal (pre-crash). gUSE-integration in M22 will also allow to finally use the service in its entirety as intended for SCI-BUS.

5.8 JRA2.8 Citizen Web Community Gateway (EG)

The Citizen Web Community Gateway is a new R&D project of E-Group in the field of Document Management Systems. E-Group has already developed complex Document Management System called eDOX and this cloud-based module shall be integrated with the Citizen Web Community Gateway based on experiences of SCI-BUS project.

The aim of this gateway is to connect the paper-based and electronic world. Nowadays, converting paper-based documents into authentic electronic documents (that also support content processing) is an emerging need on behalf of governmental and business sector. The document processing needs on-demand additional resources if automation is a requirement. This kind of document processing is also covered by legislation therefore conformance to regulations shall be guaranteed during the SCI-BUS project.

5.8.1 User Feedback, Experience

Based on our earlier experiences and user requests we successfully took part in the modification process of the relating legal background. Now, the Decree No. 13/2005. (X. 27.) of the Minister of Information and Communications on the Rules of Digitalization of Paper-based Documents supports the more automated way of document processing that fits to user requirements.

The original user need (“business pain”) came at the beginning of economic crisis: both companies and public administration decided to immediately and easily reduce operational costs, and one of the identified key projects was this kind of electronic document processing. Unfortunately, it turned out in 2009 that the legal background supported just manual content processing therefore the main goal of the decree modification was exactly enabling support of automation.

The users usually create and/or store their documents in electronic document management systems, therefore the input interface of our gateway supports the upload of electronic documents (either scanned or already digitally created ones). The results of the whole process are document packages that comply with the legislation (digitally signed, metadata enriched document). The interface for this is an easy-to-use web based portal for human users and a REST API for other entities.

Specific user requirements were:

- Better OCR results
- Better indexing results
- Certified cryptographic module
- User friendly accounting GUI

5.8.2 Existing Setup and Features in 1st release

In the 1st release the main goal was to implement the framework of the document processing workflow with cloud support.

- We developed a simple web-based GUI that supports registration and login of users, step-by-step document processing, searching.
- We deployed the computation intensive codes into the cloud. For this we used RemoteAPI web service interface of gUSE/WS-PGRADE. The Amazon EC2 and Amazon S3 are used in the background which is called via CloudBroker and DCI Bridge module of SZTAKI system.
- We used the free CuneiForm/OpenOCR software to produce the recognized (OCR – Optical Character Recognition) output of the processed document (in the cloud).
- We created some proof-of-concept dictionaries and regular expressions to extract data from the content (in the cloud).
- At the 1st release we haven't integrated the cryptographic module.

During the first part of the project the development of CloudBroker and DCI Bridge (module of gUSE/WS-PGRADE) interfaces were parallel, therefore we had to upgrade our self-installed and configured gUSE instances several times.

Figure 29: Initial Architecture

5.8.3 Additional Features in 2nd Release

Based on the testing and operational experiences of 1st release we had to re-organize the workflow and the architecture behind the whole workflow in order to be put it into production.

Figure 30: New Architecture

- In the production version of the gateway we had to change the OCR engine in order to produce high-quality outputs: from CuneiForm/OpenOCR to ABBYY FineReader 11 Corporate Edition. For licensing reasons this new OCR module was removed from the cloud and now it operates on E-GROUP side. Despite, the OCR function is computation intensive step of processing, there were no licensing option for cloud usage at the chosen software. Now, the OCR module is part of the “Gateway functional layer” (see the picture). The OCR module covers the following functionalities:

- **OCRing:**

This step covers recognition of characters (default license can be extended in order to support e.g. Asian font sets), and keeping layout layer (e.g. creating XPath-based rules for stylesheets).

- **spellchecking:**

This step covers post-processing of OCR-ized content (apprx. 200 languages are supported).

The metadata processing and indexing steps were also extended. Now, it covers the following functionalities:

- **extracting:**

This step covers dictionary-based and regular expression-based (regexp) rules in order to retrieve pre-defined expressions, words, data structures.

- **indexing:**

This step covers canonicalization of content by transforming expressions to the roots (recently available just for Hungarian).

- **ranking:**

This step covers enumerating roots, assigning counters and other ranking values based on ranking algorithm.

- **classifying:**

This step covers categorization of document based on algorithms that analyze content values and content types (e.g. the document is probably an invoice, if it contains the string "Invoice" as title, and contains date data types).

Figure 31: Metadata Processing. This covers just the workflow of metadata processing which is based on OCRized input content. Beyond these steps are also scanning, digital signature creation, accounting functions shall be performed.

Based on the modification of the legal background also some data structure should have been modified (e.g. the list and structure of metadata XML content).

- **metadating:**

This step covers the construction of XML-based (MIReG) metadata structure based on retrieved metadata of processed document.

The cryptographic module (the final step of the whole process workflow) was integrated into the portal, so now electronic signatures protect the document packages. Finally, we applied the certified cryptographic module of E-Group (instead of OpenSSL) to create electronic signatures.

- **digital signing:**

This step covers creation of XML-based (XAdES) electronic signature on a processed document and its related outputs by using a cryptographic private key (e.g. RSA), retrieving timestamp and revocation information (e.g. CRL, OCSP response).

The production version of the document processing service shall support credits of user accounts and clearing functionality. The integration of payment solution is not in the scope: there are several methods for credit top-up of a user account (e.g. money transfer to a central bank account via netbanking solution), but these methods shall be supported by the environment.

- **accounting:**

This step covers calculating accountable values based on the real usage of the service (e.g. processed page per job).

To sum up the general workflow changes:

- integration of the accounting and clearing module
- removing the OCR module from the cloud environment and integrating into our gateway
- applying the certified cryptographic module of E-Group (instead of OpenSSL)

5.8.4 eDOX Status and Plans for the Final Release

Task	Month	Status
Planning workflow based on legislation	M1	Done M1
Testing OCR softwares	M3	Done M3
Implementing "Preparation of Scanned Document module"	M4	Done M4
Implementing "Professional OCR/ICR module"	M6	Done M6

Implementing "Indexing and Metadata Processing module"	M9	Done M9
Implementing "Cryptographic Service Provider module"	M10	Done M19
Remote API implementation	M11	Done M12
First release (based on D8.1 and D8.2)	M12	Done M12
Modification of legal background	M18	Done M18
Modification of metadata schema (based on modified legal background)	M19	Done M19
Implementing clearing module	M19	Done M19
Second release	M19	Done M19
Enhancement of metadata retrieval algorithm	M24	In Progress
Enhancement of indexing algorithm	M24	In Progress
Enhancement of document type classification algorithm	M24	In Progress
Enhancement of ranking algorithm	M35	In Progress
Third release	M35	Planned

5.8.5 Operation and Testing Status

The database module of the system is periodically archived, while stateless modules – such as indexing, ranking services that immediately write back results into database – have just one snapshot as backup. The logs – that are also sent back and stored in the database – are analyzed in case of errors, bug reports are created and assigned to developers.

The tests – implemented and executed periodically by 4DSoft – covers all the needed interfaces of publicly available portal. The tests are executed weekly and summary of results are sent directly to E-GROUP via e-mail.

5.9 JRA2.9 Astrophysics Community Science Gateway (INAF)

INAF has integrated the existing VisIVOWeb and VisIVO Smartphone applications with the WS-PGRADE gateway in the VisIVO Science Gateway. It offers new, exciting and easily accessible opportunities not only to specialized users, e.g. astrophysical researchers, but also to the wider public, e.g. high-school education or innovative citizen science for new scientific developments.

VisIVO Science Gateway, available at the following URL: <http://visivo.oact.inaf.it:8080>, integrates seamlessly large-scale multi-dimensional astrophysical datasets with applications for processing and visualization based on Distributed Computing Infrastructures (DCIs). A number of customized workflows are stored on the gateway repository to allow local or remote uploading of datasets, datasets filtering and creation of scientific movies. These workflows are provided with specific portlets to enable intuitive parameter setting for standard users while hiding the complexity of the underlying system and infrastructures.

The **VisIVO Mobile** application allows smartphone devices to exploit VisIVO Science Gateway functionalities to access large-scale astrophysical datasets residing on a server repository for analysis and visual discovery and to submit the implemented workflows stored in the gateway repository.

5.9.1 User Feedback, Experience

Most of the users have experience in the use of complex computing infrastructures, so the employed underlying computing technologies are not new for them. Nevertheless they appreciated the easy user interface setup of the underlying workflows executing the computational tasks. The user interfaces guide the users to import and process their dataset via several portlets and the most appreciated feature is the possibility to browse through their datasets and produced images and movies via the FileManagement portlet.

The users reported some enhancement requests for the Gateway in the survey attached to deliverable D2.5 and via e-mail (visivo-support@oact.inaf.it). In summary, the feedback was:

- Some users experienced problems in importing some dataset formats (e.g. RawBin or Fly formats) from the VisIVOImporter portlet.
- It was requested to fix some bugs in the FileManagement portlet to enhance its usability e.g. in dragging items.
- Users requested to extend the meta data information associated to each imported dataset (e.g. show the histogram of each field in logarithmic scale).

In addition, INAF provides workflows for several specialized astrophysics communities: the Muon Portal project community⁹, the Large Simulation for Modified Gravity (LaSMoG) consortium at ICG (University of Portsmouth), and the Stellar Model Simulations team (INAF, Teramo), to exploit the functionalities of the gateway. Several complex workflows have been designed and developed for these communities. For each workflow an ASM portlet was created to support input parameters configuration.

5.9.2 Existing setup and Features in 1st Release

The 1st release of the VisIVO Science Gateway supported the usage of WS P-GRADE/gUSE Version 3.4.4. It contained the following portlets already documented in D8.2:

- **VisIVO Importer**: this ASM portlet converts user datasets into VisIVO Binary Tables (VBTs) internal format and extract all necessary meta data providing the dataset for further exploration to the portal.

⁹ <http://muoni.oact.inaf.it:8080/en>

- **VisIVO Filters:** this ASM portlet converts imported datasets from an original data table into a new one performing several operations (e.g. can create a Volume from a table)
- **VisIVO Viewer:** this portlet displays customized views of 3D renderings.
- **Properties:** displays the meta data of the imported datasets and produced images.
- **Data Management:** this portlet allows the management of imported datasets and produced images and movies and allows the navigation within the different services offered by the portal.
- **Panoramic and Dynamic Movie:** this ASM portlet creates scientific movies using a produced image.
- **Custom Movie:** this ASM portlet creates scientific movies starting from all produced images using an imported dataset.

The workflows implemented in the 1st release related to the aforementioned portlets are:

- VisIVO Importer Workflows access the VisIVO Importer tool:
 - ✓ **Importer:** this workflow imports a dataset into a VBT extracting useful meta data such as basic statistics and histograms of the fields or the first rows in a textual file.
 - ✓ **RemoteImporter:** this workflow imports a remote dataset into a VBT extracting useful meta data such as basic statistics and histograms of the fields or the first rows in a textual file and send an e-mail after the completion.
 - ✓ **Multimporter:** this workflow imports a dataset into a set of VBTs (e.g. in case of GADGET data) extracting useful meta data such as basic statistics and histograms of the fields or the first rows in a textual file.
 - ✓ **RemoteMultimporter:** this workflow imports a remote dataset into a set of VBTs (e.g. in case of GADGET data) extracting useful meta data such as basic statistics and histograms of the fields or the first rows in a textual file and send an e-mail after the completion.
- VisIVO Filters Workflows access the VisIVO Filters tool:
 - ✓ **Filters:** this workflow applies a VisIVO filter to a VBT generating a new VBT and relative meta-data.
 - ✓ **SplitFilter:** this workflow applies a VisIVO filter split operation to a VBT generating a set of new VBTs and relative meta-data.
 - ✓ **StatFilter:** this workflow performs a statistic VisIVO filter operation on a VBT generating a set of statistics of the VBT fields.
 - ✓ **WriteVO Filter:** this workflow writes a VO Table corresponding to a VBT.
- Scientific Movies Workflows: they access *VisIVO Utils* tools to create camera path for *VisIVO Viewer* and employs *ffmpeg* to generate a movie
 - ✓ **Panoramic Movie:** this workflow generates four camera path corresponding to a rotation of 360° in azimuth and 180° in elevation and generate the corresponding movies using a Parameter Sweep operation which are finally merged into the final movie.
 - ✓ **Generic Movie:** this workflow generates a camera path corresponding to a user defined path and generates the corresponding final movie.
 - ✓ **Dynamic Movie:** this workflow generates dynamic movie interpolating several steps of a time evolution of a cosmological dataset (in VBT format).

The VisIVO Mobile application was developed to allow smartphone devices to exploit VisIVO Science Gateway functionalities to access large-scale astrophysical datasets residing on a server repository for analysis and visual discovery. Through interactive widgets, customized visualizations (images or movies) can be generated and stored on the remote server. The application notifies users when requested visualizations are available for retrieving on their smartphones and allows easy sharing of data, images and movies via e-mail or common social networks.

5.9.3 Additional Features in 2nd Release

To enhance the usability of the VisIVO Science Gateway and to meet the user requests the following activities have been performed:

- The VisIVO Science Gateway was upgraded to gUSE/WSPGrade version 3.5.6 (also the development instance of the gateway supports version 3.5.6)
- The portlet codes have been refactored to be easily re-distributable:
 - 1) hard coded parameters have been removed;
 - 2) a new VisIVOWebUtils .jar library has been implemented for general purpose utilities;
 - 3) the portlet code has been update to use gUSE ASM API version 3.4.4;
- The VisIVO Importer and VisIVO Filters workflows have been consolidated and they have been updated to generate new statistics and meta-data to be visualized via the Properties portlet.
- The 1st release portlets has been updated to remove bugs and enhance their usability.
- A User Forum was added under the “Contacts” menu item and contains the threads grouped in four categories for VisIVO Importer, Filters, Viewer and Scientific Movie issues.
- The Documentation was upgraded to reflect the new functionalities.

Additionally the 2nd release of the gateway contains a number of challenging workflows which has been prototyped to support highly specialized scientific communities in astrophysics:

- **Muon Portal:** this workflow was developed to support the Muon Portal project which aims at detecting nuclear threat materials carried into cargo containers exploiting the muon particles coming from the secondary radiation of the sun.
- **LaSMoG:** this workflow was designed to support the LaSMoG consortium in the University of Portsmouth to compare modified gravity models (i.e. without introducing dark energy) with the standard dark energy models.
- **FRANEC:** this workflow was designed to run FRANEC numerical code to support INAF-Teramo community. This code is perfectly suited for computing evolutions of stars on the basis of a number of different physical inputs and parameters.

Advanced users can exploit such workflows as templates for building new customized workflows to suit particular requirements of scientific communities, e.g. by modifying appropriately constituent building blocks customized LaSMoG workflows can be generated. Standard users can then execute these workflows in an interactive and user-friendly way by means of the supplied portlets (implemented using the gUSE ASM API) under the menu “Community”.

Figures below show the developed portlets, the main functionalities of the underlying workflows and some example results.

Figure 32: Muon Portal processing portlet, workflow and some results showing the simulated nuclear material inside the container

Figure 33: LaSMoG processing portlet, workflow and some results showing the visual comparison between the modified gravity model (D_M) and the standard gravity model (D_S) and the volume rendering resulting from their difference (V_Δ)

Figure 34: FRANEK processing portlet, workflow and some results of the stellar evolution simulation

The VisIVO Mobile application has been extended to support the new gateway functionalities. New interfaces have been developed to configure the Muon Portal, LaSMoG and FRANEK workflows to be submitted using the gUSE Remote API. Additionally some efforts have been put, collaborating with JRA1, to integrate the WSPgrade/gUSE utilities to create, configure and submit a new workflow directly from the mobile application. So far the mobile application has been customized to the astrophysics community but these new functionalities will be more general to all the other communities.

Figure 35: VisIVO Mobile Application: muon portal workflow configuration (left figure), workflow graph creation (right figure)

5.9.4 VisIVO Status and Plans for the Final Release

Future releases of the VisIVO Science Gateway will include bug fixes of the deployed portlets and workflows and improve the usability of the gateway following user feedback and requests for improvements.

A public release of VisIVO Mobile is planned for the end of M24, it will be published on the iOS App Store and source code will be available on request sending a mail to visivo-support@oact.inaf.it.

The detailed planning according to milestones are summarized in the table below:

Task	Month	Status
WS-PGRADE	M2	Done M2
Purchase new Hardware	M2	Done M2
Web Interface Design	M2	Done M2
gUSE Remote Api	M3	Done M4
VisIVO Mobile Design	M4	Done M4
VisIVO Gateway Internal Testing	M4	Done M4
Testing plan SA2	M4	Done M4
Workflows Design	M6	Done M6
VisIVO Importer Workflow	M9	Done M9
VisIVO Filters Workflow	M9	Done M9
VisIVO Movie Workflows	M9	Done M10
Web Interface: Update Layout	M10	Done M10
Web Interface: Cleanup code	M10	Done M13
Testing with SA2 (VisIVO Science Gateway)	M10	Done M13
Add new Specialized Workflows	M19	Done M19
UI Enhancements	M20	Done M20
VisIVO Mobile Updates	M20	Done M20
VisIVO Mobile Public Release	M24	In Progress

5.9.5 Operation and Testing status

The VisIVO Science Gateway is in production and it has more than twenty users and they have run thousands of jobs. Based on the gathered user feedbacks several improvements on the portlets and workflows were done and three new portlets and workflows were implemented for specialized astrophysics communities. The user documentation has been improved and it is regularly updated and a user forum was added to the gateway.

The web tests, implemented and executed periodically by 4DSoft, covers all the needed interfaces of the gateway. The tests are executed weekly and summary of results are sent directly to INAF via e-mail. As future plans tests for the VisIVO Mobile Application are under investigation.

5.10 JRA2.10 Build and Test Public Gateway for Application Developers (4D)

Build and Test Portal is an out-of-the box web application for

- Building/testing software projects continuously, making it easier for developers to integrate changes to the project, making it easier for testers to run tests just after the build and for end users to obtain a new build.
- Monitoring jobs and detailed reporting of the results
- Repository for software packages and reports

The Build and Test Portal existed as a GWT-based web application submitting jobs on local cluster served by Condor/NMI based job submission middleware. We have integrated the portal with the services provided by gUSE to extend the existing job submission capabilities with a more flexible, user centric cloud infrastructure. To do so, a local instance of the WS-PGRADE portal was installed. Remote API is invoked to submit build jobs to the cloud. The motivation to move to cloud is that we are going to run the Gateway as an SaaS serving a large number of user communities. Cloud integration is the most important implementation task to achieve this goal. In this release we could submit jobs to the virtual machine set up according to our requirements on OpenNebula, hosted by SZTAKI, through the CloudBroker plugin and DCI Bridge component of the WS-PGRADE portal. The upgraded portal is available at etics3-test.4dsoft.hu.

As of the latest release, using this portal, the users can submit their build jobs to the local cluster or to a virtual machine residing on the OpenNebula cloud infrastructure hosted by SZTAKI and accessed through the DCI Bridge/CloudBroker interface.

5.10.1 User Feedback, Experience

In the 1st release we integrated our portal with DCI Bridge at job submission level. For convenience, low level job (JSDL) submission was chosen (not workflow based) – as it fit better in the job submission approach of the Build and Test Portal.

In order to implement this architecture, service level DCI Bridge integration was required with the already available build and test services. To do so, a couple of web services of the DCI Bridge component were installed in the machine where the Build Portal is running. JSDL based job description files were generated in the Build and Test Portal. Those JSDL files (not workflows) have been submitted to the web services of the DCI Bridge.

The shortcomings of this architecture were revealed early in the pilot phase. The most severe issues we faced were due to authentication problems. As authentication can be done at workflow level only, there was no possibility to authenticate with the CloudBroker plugin in this way. The installed web services were not able to do proper authentication. Additionally, low level job submission functionalities were not supported by SZTAKI. No documentation is available at that level.

As a final conclusion, we decided to change the architecture.

5.10.2 Existing Setup and Features in 1st release

Making use of the cloud DCI extension for the Build and Test Portal means to make use of virtual machines residing on cloud infrastructures as build servers additionally to the build servers registered in the local cluster.

In order to extend the existing portal with cloud resources, the following major additions have to be made in the first release.

First, the web interface of the Build and Test Portal making use of the newly implemented cloud integration has been modified. Now the users can select cloud resources as option when configuring build or test jobs. More precisely, users can select the option to run the build jobs on the local cluster or on the virtual machine hosted by OpenNebula. The first version of this user interface modification has been available in the 1st release and it was extended for the 2nd release version.

Second, we integrated our portal with the DCI Bridge at job submission level with the already available build and test services, such as configuration, job submission and job repository. As the DCI Bridge was not released as a separate component at that time, to have all this in place, a few of the web services of the gUSE/WS-PGRADE portal were deployed.

The jobs were described using the jsdl - job description language applied for most DCI. The 1st version of our gateway we could submit jobs through the DCI Bridge to the local resource. As described in Section 5.10.1 it was revealed early in the experimentation phase that this architecture is not appropriate. For that reason, we opted to submit jobs at workflow level through the DCI Bridge/CloudBroker plugin using the Remote API of the gUSE/WS-PGRADE portal family (see section 5.10.3 for more detail).

Some parts of this implementation have been reused in the 2nd release as well. For example, a service called RunnerThread had been implemented to monitor the job status and to register the resulted artefacts in the repository of the Build and Test Portal. The first version of this service was available in the 1st release and it was extended in the second release.

5.10.3 Additional Features in 2nd Release

As stated in the previous section, we opted for a new architecture. We installed a WS-PGRADE portal, which is available now locally (<http://guse.4dsoft.hu>). We also installed the Remote API on that machine.

At the same time, we created an Ubuntu based virtual machine (VM). On that VM we installed all the external software packages required for running build and test jobs. Among others, Java, Python, Openssl, etc have been deployed. This VM is deployed on the OpenNebula hosted by SZTAKI.

Next, we created and configured a single-node workflow in our WS-PGRADE portal. This particular workflow has one input – the job ID of the build and test job coming from the Build and Test Portal – and one output for the results coming back from the cloud. We always use this workflow, it is just the input – the job ID coming from the Build and Test Portal – that is different every time.

Finally, a particular wrapper script for the build and test job has been deployed into the CloudBroker platform.

Having all that put together, we configured the workflow in the DCI Bridge component to run in the VM in OpenNebula through the CloudBroker platform. The workflow submission is done using the Remote API. Also the results are retrieved through the Remote API. As a last step, the results (reports and software packages) are registered in the internal repository of the Build and Test Portal.

Regarding the user interface, the users can select cloud resources as an option when configuring build or test jobs. Then they can follow the status of the jobs in the 'Submission' portlet. The figure below shows the architecture.

Figure 36: Build and Test Portal extension with cloud

5.10.4 Testing Gateway Status and Plans

The most important task of our Gateway has been to extend it with cloud resources. The first working version of this important task was realised in M20. It is publicly available.

For the remainder of the project, we are going to test extensively and improve the cloud integration. An additional task is to improve the currently existing UI and to add more community functions. A Liferay based solution will be added as a welcome page to our existing portal. This task is under work.

The table below summarises the most important planned tasks. Then there is a section on the current status and a short section on the future plans.

Tasks	Month	Status
WS-PGRADE, gUSE installation	M2	Done M2
Initial design of the new submission service	M3	Done M3
Test Plan	M4	Done M4
Redesign of the submission service	M5	Done M5
UI changes	M6	Done M7
gUSE, WS-PGRADE portal built from the CloudBroker integration development branch	1 st year release	Done M8
jsdl based job description adoption	1 st year release	Done M10
Job monitoring & register thread implementation	1 st year release	Done M11
Registration in repository	1 st year release	Done M12
Deployment tests	1 st year release	Done M10
New Remote API based architecture for cloud extension	2 nd year release	Done M20
Web tests	2 st year release	In progress
UI enhancements	2 nd year release	In progress

Status

- WS-PGRADE portal and Remote API are installed in our local servers
- Virtual machine (VM) with the necessary test environment is deployed on OpenNebula
- Remote API based workflow submission through the DCI Bridge/CloudBroker plugin to the VM on SZTAKI hosted OpenNebula is operational
- A new job status monitoring and register service has been implemented
- Deployment packages and (build, tests) reports registration to the repository is done.
- A public instance containing the new implementations (etics3-test.4dsoft.hu) has been set up and is operational. Currently whoever is interested in the usage of the gateway can initiate the registration process. We are going to improve that process to have a more straightforward registration in the next coming period.
- Liferay based welcome page for community functions is under work. Also the dashboard portlet is improving.
- Scheduled weekly builds for the Build and Test Portal are running.
- Web Testing has been started.

5.11 JRA2.11 Helio-Physics Gateway (TCD)

Heliophysics is the branch of physics that investigates the relationship among the various bodies of the Solar System, more precisely; it investigates how the Sun influences the Heliosphere. The investigative domain of heliophysics is thus the entire Solar System, an extremely vast “experimental space” where phenomena propagate from the Sun to the outer bodies. Data is gathered from a multiple of sensors on board satellites and on the surface of the planets.

Successful investigation in heliophysics entails coordinated analysis of data gathered across the entire Solar System regarding phenomena that evolve in space and time. Two recurring problems in the heliophysics community are to model how phenomena propagate throughout the Solar System and, of course, processing of potentially high quantities of raw data.

Compared to other communities, the Heliophysics community has some original traits that are worth mentioning:

1. It is a small community focused on a niche research
2. It is relatively new to workflows
3. It heavily relies on various catalogues that list events and features. These catalogues are based on already existing metadata or on the extraction of metadata from raw data.

In their investigations, heliophysicists can rely on many different resources spanning from existing catalogues of features and events to publicly available tools for the processing of data. HELIOGate relies on many such services and procedures that have been developed during the HELIO project; an FP7 funded initiative that produced a Virtual Observatory based on multi-layered service oriented architecture.

The HELIOGate portal¹⁰ focuses on two aspects of Heliophysics, propagation models and data processing. It has developed a portlet for the study of the propagation of Coronal Mass Ejections (Advanced Propagation Model) and it has developed workflows for the processing of data.

The Advanced Propagation Model

Heliophysics deals with phenomena that span the entire Solar System, to investigate them, scientist must first find relevant events and then try to understand how they propagate from the Sun throughout the Solar System. To find relevant events, heliophysicists can rely on various catalogues that are available on line. The analysis of propagation is tackled by specific physical and mathematical models called “Propagation Models”

Standard Propagation Models require users to enter parameters to deliver accurate results but these parameters are not always easy to estimate and force users to guess them either from other sources of data or from their experience; this step can be very complicated and force users to take wild guesses.

HELIOGate proposes a different approach, its Advanced Propagation Model require its users to only indicate a range of reasonable values and executes in a parameter sweep fashion the

¹⁰ <http://portal02.cs.tcd.ie:8080/liferay-portal-6.1.0/web/guest/heliogate1>

propagation model for all the values within the ranges. The full list of results is then presented to the user for a validation step performed by querying catalogues of events (that were observed throughout the Solar System) to find if a certain parameter is compatible with events both at the origin and the target; usually the Sun and a Planet or artificial satellite.

5.11.1 *User Feedback, Experience*

Although the concept of the advanced propagation model is quite useful, the first release of the portlet has several shortcomings that hinder its usability. The shortcomings of this implementation can be summarized in

Table 1.

Short-coming	Description	Relevance
A	User has to manually enter the catalogue of events to be used. This is error prone and requires the user to have information of the existing catalogues	Medium
B	User cannot select one or more events in step 2. This forces the system to always execute the model for all the events while some may not be significant.	Medium
C	User can select only ranges for the lift off speed of CMES. Other parameters should be defined as ranges, if the users want.	Medium
D	The system can only model CMEs (Coronal Mass Ejections). The system can only model events forward while at times it is useful to trace back from the target body to the sun.	High
E	The system can take a long time to execute the model.	High
F	The entire approach to the propagation model is somehow rigid. The possibility of finding events in one catalogue can be overly restrictive and ranking parameters only based on the report of one event at target as it is now in the portlet, can lead to very limited results. Ideally, a user should be able to define in liberty how to find the events, how to model their propagation and how to validate the results. This goal is too complicated to achieve as it cannot be modelled easily, especially for what regards the interface but a good approach where the propagation model is broken into sub workflows that users can modify can prove very profitable.	Medium

Table 1, HELIOGate Feedback

We are developing the 2nd release of the Advanced Propagation Model to take into account these requirements.

5.11.2 Existing Setup and Features in 1st Release

The First Release portlet developed for the Advanced Propagation model leads users through a five steps process as described in the table below:

Step	Description	ScreenShot
1	The user selects a time range and a catalogue of events to find the phenomena that she/he wants to investigate	
2	The user is given a list of events that are relevant in the time range. The user defines the ranges of the parameters for which to execute the propagation model.	

3 The user is given a list of the model execution with a rank (if an event observed at the target, the system ranks the parameter to 1)

4 The user then selects the propagation model executed with the right parameter and investigates the results

Table 2, Execution Steps for the Advanced Propagation Model Portlet

The HELIOGate Infrastructure

HELIOGate is based on the infrastructure described in Figure 37.

Figure 37, Hardware Architecture of HELIOGate

HELIOGate comprises 4 main components:

- **Portals.** The three main HELIOGate portals (Production, Development and Testing) are XEN virtual images hosted in Dell 2950 with 16 GB RAM and 80 GB Hard Disk. Each portal has all the components (gUSE, MySQL and DCIBridge) installed in the same Virtual Machines.
- **Processing Component.** The processing is performed by a 216 core Torque cluster composed by:
 - Torquehead: A Dell R510
 - 16 worker nodes: Dell R410 – 2x Intel Xeon X5650 @ 2.67 GHz - 24 cores - 48 GB of memory – 500GB disks)
- **Storage:** Up to 80TB of storage facilities are available composed by:
 - Frontend Storage: DELL2950
 - Several DELL MD1000 (Disk Arrays – 2TB disks in RAID 6 configuration)
- **Networking:** Internal networking connecting storage, cluster and portals with bandwidth of 1GB/sec and external connection

At the moment the HELIOGate community is not yet in production status as there are still some remaining problems regarding the maintenance and provisioning of the infrastructure. A solution using puppet¹¹ is currently been deployed but the stability of the system is not yet

¹¹ <https://puppetlabs.com/>

in production status. We foresee that HELIOGate will be in full production status at the end of M23 of the project.

5.11.3 *Additional Features in 2nd Release*

The second release of the Advanced Propagation Model (expected to be completed in M23) portlet tackles the shortcomings of Release 1 as described in

Table 3

Shortcoming	Description
A	Allow the user to select catalogues from a list.
B	Allow users to select one or more events.
C	Allow user to define ranges for other parameters
D	Extend the Advanced Propagation model to Solar Winds and Solar Energetic Particles
E	Execute the model in parallel over a cluster.
F	Expresses the propagation models as sub-workflows that can be replaced

Table 3, Characteristics of Release 2

To implement the 2nd release of the advanced propagation model we have created the workflow described in Figure 38.

Figure 38, Workflow that described the Advanced Propagation Model

This workflow covers all the steps of the Advanced Propagation Model, this allows a greater flexibility in all the steps in respect of Release 1 where all the steps except the execution of the model itself where expressed as code in the portlet and not in workflows.

To allow control of each part of the process in an easier way, the workflow in Figure 38, has been broken into the workflows described in

Step	Workflow	Meaning
	SourceEventFinder	Given a list of catalogues an extraction criteria returns a VOTable with the list of all relevant events

	<p>ParameterExtractor</p>	<p>Given a list of events, it extracts the parameter values or ranges that are relevant for the execution of the propagation model.</p>
	<p>TimeExtractor</p>	<p>Given a list of events, it extracts the time values or ranges that are relevant for the execution of the propagation model.</p>
	<p>Propagator</p>	<p>It invokes the SHEBA propagation model with the parameters and times produced by ParameterExtractor and TimeExtractor</p>
	<p>Ranker</p>	<p>It ranks the results of the propagation model.</p>

Table 4,Breakdown of the propagation model workflow

The second release of the Advanced Propagation Model is based on the architecture described in Figure 39, **Architecture of the second release of the APM** .

Figure 39, Architecture of the second release of the APM gateway

The architecture is composed of the following components.

Interfaces	The workflows of the Advanced Propagation model can be executed either through the WS-PGRADE easy user interface of HELIOGate or through the deployed ASM based portlet.
GUSE and DCI Bridge services	The workflows are stored and executed through invocation of the ASM services. These invocations, in turn, access the resources
Catalogue access programs	When workflows that access catalogues are executed, they invoke Catalogue access programs that connect with the Helio Event Catalogue (HEC) web service.
Propagation Model scripts	Scripts that execute the IDL routines of the SHEBA propagation model. SHEBA uses routines present in the SSW library.

Data Processing Workflows

HELIOGate is now engaged with the Heliophysics team of TCD to support the data processing requirements of the group. In order to do so, four generic workflows have been developed to help the team in executing data processing in an efficient and re-usable way.

The main use case for the data processing involves the extraction of features from the data coming from the LO-FAR project¹², but similar use cases have suggested to produce generic, multi-purpose workflows.

An analysis with the developers highlighted 5 different stages for all the use cases that was used to define the workflows describe in **Table 5**.

Name	Image
CompleteGenericProcessing	
LocalGenericProcessing	
CompleteSimpleProcessing	
LocalSimpleProcessing	

Table 5, Generic Workflows for Data Processing

As all workflows are reduced versions of the CompleteGeneralProcessing workflow, we illustrate only this in

Step	Description
DataStaging	Downloads data from external sources and stores it in the storage facility of HELIOGate
PreProcessing	Checks that all resources (external services, downloaded data) needed for the execution of the data processing code are present.

¹² <http://www.lofar.org/>

Processing	The data processing it self
PostProcessing	Checks that the produced metadata is consistent and correct, wipes the data downloaded in DataStaging if it is not needed for further executions
DataPublishing	Copies the metadata produced by the code on external resources.

Table 6, Steps of the Complete General Processing workflow

5.11.4 HELIOGate Portal Status and Plans

The number of members of the community is at the moment rather limited (less than 10 registered users) due to concurring factors:

- The small size of the Heliophysics community itself
- The current prototypical nature of the portal

In order to increase the number of users to HELIOGate, TCD plans to:

- Move to full production the HELIOGate portal for a better quality of service
- Deploy the new releases of the Propagation Model applications that are more flexible and cover more physical phenomena (Solar Winds and Solar Energetic Particles)
- Engage users that develop data processing procedures for the LO-FAR data (Generic Processing Workflows)
- Connect the HELIOGate portal to the SHIWA repository so that the workflows ported in the ER-FLOW project can be executed through the HELIOGate portal

The detailed planning is summarized in the table below.

Task	Month	Status
WS-Pgrade and gUse connection with IDL environment	M9	Done M9
Portal proof of concept	M9	Done M12
First prototype	M15	Done M16
Definition of Features for the second prototype	M15	Done M16
Advanced Propagation Workflows for Release 2	M21	Done M21
Generic Data Processing Workflows	NA	Done M20
Connection to SHIWA	NA	Work in Progress (M21)
Implementation of second prototype (points D and E)	M21	Work in Progress (M22-M23)
Implementation of second prototype (points A, B, C and F)	M21	Work in Progress (M23)

5.11.5 Operation and Testing Status

Testing strategy of the advanced propagation portlet has been implemented and is executed weekly. TCD receives a weekly email with the status of the test.

The HELIOGate portal is running approximately 2 months late due to a combination of factors among which the most prominent are delays in the setup of the production environment and in the development of the second release of the APM portlet. These delays had some impact on the possible amount of users. We are planning to rectify this situation by the end of M23